

**National
Council of
Churches'
Review**

NCC REVIEW

Vol. CXLIV

No. 5

June 2024

UGC-CARE List ISSN 0975 - 1882

The National Council of Churches Review (NCC Review)

The Organ of the National Council of Churches in India

UGC approved Journal

Formerly published as "The Harvest Field" since 1862

Vol. CXLIV

No. 5

June 2024

Contents

EDITORIAL

Democracy and 'Epistocracy': Insights from Indian Experiences

Abraham Mathew----- 235

ARTICLES

Locating Delhi Farmers Protests of

2020-21 as an Environmental Justice Movement

Justin Mathew----- 238

Dynamics of Socialisation of

Shadowed Fair Sex: Historic Initiatives of Breklum Mission in Koraput

Raghumani Naik----- 252

Resurrected Body – Thomistic Re-reading on Aristotle's

Body-Soul Relation: A New Perspective

Gasper K. J.----- 264

Imperial Tactics and Resilience:

A Childist Perspective on Mephibosheth's Journey

Sam T Rajkumar----- 273

100 Years Ago – From NCC Review----- 286

NCCI NEWS----- 290

WCC NEWS----- 294

CCA NEWS----- 296

GLOBAL CHRISTIAN FORUM----- 297

BIBLE STUDY

Joseph's Narrative as a Paradigm Towards True Stewardship

Imtikumla Aier----- 300

Editor, Publisher & Printer: Rev. Dr. Asir Ebenezer, National Council of Churches in India, P.B. No.: 205, Civil Lines, Nagpur - 440 001, Maharashtra India, **Phone:** +91712-2531312, 2561464 Fax: +91-712-2520554 **Email:** <nccreview@ncci1914.com> **Managing**

Editor: Rev. Dr. Abraham Mathew, Executive Secretary, Policy, Governance and Public Witness. **Editorial Board:** Dr. Y. Pammeleena, Dr. Sundeep Chaudhary, Rev. Dr. Y. T. Vinayraj, Dr. Shiju Sam Varughese, Dr. S. Johnson Jeyakumar **Printed at:** Shyam Brothers, Near ST Stand, Ganeshpeth, Nagpur **Owner:** Rev. Dr. Asir Ebenezer, National Council of Churches in India **Place of Publication:** National Council of Churches in India, P.B. No.: 205, Civil Lines, Nagpur-440 001, Maharashtra, India **Place of Printing:** Shyam Bros, Near ST Stand, Ganeshpeth, Nagpur **Website:** <https://ncci1914.com/ncc-review/>

Views expressed in the NCC Review do not necessarily reflect the official position of the National Council of Churches in India

Registration No. 33/2019

EDITORIAL

Democracy and ‘Epistocracy’: Insights from Indian Experiences

Georgetown political philosopher Jason Brennan’s 2016 book *Against Democracy* argues that democracy is overrated and does not necessarily lead to more just or equitable outcomes. He critiques democracy’s effectiveness and suggests replacing it with “epistocracy,” a system where the votes of politically knowledgeable citizens hold more weight than those of less informed voters. Brennan’s proposal challenges the conventional view of democracy by emphasizing that informed decision-making may lead to better governance, despite its controversial nature. His critique explores the moral and structural limitations of democratic systems.

Criticism of democracy is not new. Historically, intellectuals have pointed out issues with citizens’ ignorance. Socrates believed that ‘voting is a skill, not a matter of random intuition’, and thus requires systematic education. His disciple, Plato, proposed an idealistic system where power was entrusted to carefully educated guardians, shielded from distractions.

Critiques of democracy continued during the Enlightenment. Thomas Hobbes, a prominent Enlightenment philosopher, argued that democracy could lead to instability, conflict, glory-seeking and mistrust, potentially undermining the social contract. Meanwhile, John Stuart Mill, examining India from a colonial perspective, proposed granting additional votes to the educated to mitigate the effects of ignorance. In the U.S., literacy tests were used to disenfranchise marginalized groups until their ban in 1975. It is a fact that voters’ lack of knowledge can endanger elections and, by extension, democracy.

India, which does not meet John Stuart Mill’s criteria for democracy—such as high literacy, elevated standards of living, and a common language system—nevertheless chose to grant voting rights without regard to literacy, income, property, or gender. At the time of independence, India had a literacy rate of just 17%, over 60% of the population lived in poverty, and the country was home to more than twenty spoken languages. Despite these formidable obstacles, India’s

early leaders decided that each citizen, regardless of their deprivation, could be trusted to understand their own interests just as well as the privileged could understand theirs.

India, the world's largest democracy, recently reached a significant milestone with its latest parliamentary elections. The election, which spanned seven phases from April 19 to June 1, 2024, chose all 543 members of the Lok Sabha. The results, announced on June 4, led to the formation of the 18th Lok Sabha. The National Democratic Alliance (NDA), led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, secured the support of 293 MPs, ensuring his third term as Prime Minister. However, the opposition parties altogether could secure almost equal number of seats receiving the mandate of people to function as checking force in democracy.

This election is noteworthy for further studies. It demonstrates how Indian voters, including those in states like Uttar Pradesh, exercised their franchise wisely, giving equal importance to opposition parties. In an era where democracy seems to be shifting towards majoritarian rule, it is crucial to uphold democratic values by establishing institutional mechanisms that prevent the dominance of a purely majoritarian approach. The involvement of ordinary citizens in this process is particularly thought-provoking.

The Indian experience offers a valuable counterpoint to Jason Brennan's concept of 'epistocracy'. Rather than viewing voters' social situations as secondary, Indian voters demonstrate that their day-to-day experiences can shape politics and that politics, in turn, can address their adverse social and economic conditions. This perspective challenges the notion that governance is best left to a politically knowledgeable elite.

However, this does not mean we should be fully optimistic about the current democratic pattern in India. We must remain vigilant regarding how the democratic process can amplify cultural majoritarianism and provoke fears among minority communities. Such dynamics often lead to institutionalised prejudice and sporadic violence against marginalised groups. This election highlighted that, despite the polarizing pressures to conform to the tyranny of the majority, people at the grassroots level still seek a harmonious life and resist the erosion of civility.

The challenge facing the newly elected government is to ensure that all citizens are fully engaged and represented in every aspect of socio-economic life. While promises of financial inclusion and development are being made, there must be a shift towards a more holistic approach that allows spaces for everyone to participate actively. This approach avoids paternalism and fosters genuine engagement from all individuals. Ultimately, the everyday experiences of people reveal both the strengths and shortcomings of Indian democracy, making it a rich subject for further academic exploration.

Rev. Dr. Abraham Mathew
Managing Editor

NCCI Women's Concern promotes

THURSDAYS IN BLACK

Campaign

in Churches and Christian/Ecumenical Organisations

To address

GENDER INJUSTICE

particularly Domestic Violence and Rape

Need Help?

Feel Free to call: 9455059522 / mail us your concern:

jyoti@ncci1914.com; ncci@ncci1914.com

LOCATING DELHI FARMERS PROTESTS OF 2020-21 AS AN ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE MOVEMENT

- Justin Mathew*

Abstract:

Neoliberal economic policies, which reduce everything to exchange value, made a deeper impact on agricultural activities on a global scale. Farm production has made a drastic transformation from a way of life to a medium to industrially accumulate natural resources. This process involves the elimination of farmers' autonomy and large-scale corporate grab of farmland. The growing drive towards industrial agriculture leads to farmers resistance movements to preserve their autonomy to cultivate and to oppose corporate land grabs. This article argues that the protest of the farmers has to be located as a part of a long struggle of the Indian farmers to defend their sovereignty against the neoliberal market forces. While the majority of newspaper articles and research papers on the farmers' movement focus on contemporary socio-political contexts, it is imperative to adopt a historically informed environmental justice perspective to fully comprehend the significance of the Delhi farmers' movement as a right-to-nature movement against the free market utopia. The intensified neoliberal appropriation of cultivable fields raises a new set of demands for economic and environmental justice. Therefore, examining the Delhi farmers' movement through the lens of environmental justice is crucial to align the movement as a part of global level right to nature movements by farmers, fishers, pastoralists, forest users, and indigenous people.

Keywords: Farmers' Movement, Environmental Justice, Right to Nature, Industrial agriculture, Agricultural marketing acts.

The year 2020 shall be marked in history as the time of the COVID-19 pandemic that reshaped the lives of ordinary people. Amidst the hardship caused by job losses, food scarcity, and strained medical facilities, the marginalized social sections were heavily burdened. The issue of amplifying inequalities forced the poor, especially the poor

* Justin Mathew is an Associate Professor in the Department of History, Hansraj College, University of Delhi.

migrant workers to leave the cities. However, Delhi, the capital city of India, experienced another significant event.

The borders of Delhi, especially Singhu and Tikri urban gateways witnessed a massive influx of farmers from nearby states, forming a powerful movement against hurriedly passed Farm Bills passed by the Government of India. While the world attempted to grapple with the Pandemic, the Government of India enacted three farm bills to reform India's agricultural sector. They were: 1) the Farmers' Produce Trade and Commerce (Promotion and Facilitation) Bill, 2020, 2) the Farmers (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance and Farm Services Bill, 2020, and the Essential commodities (Amendment) Act, 2020. Various farmers' collectives contended that the new amendments to the farm laws could potentially grant large corporate entities unchecked authority, leading to corporate monopoly over agriculture. The *Samyukta Kisan Morcha* (United Farmers Front), a collective platform representing farmers, played a crucial role in organizing the year-long protest. They pointed out that the bills were passed without consultation with the affected social groups and alleged that these legislative reforms included the rollback of welfare schemes, especially the state guarantee of a minimum support price to the crops produced by farmers, and promoted corporate farming that could adversely affect the small farmers.

Farmers organizations started arguing that these farm bills could expose the Indian agricultural sector to market forces by dismantling the narrowly remaining state protection and undermining farmers' autonomy. Additionally, these bills had the potential to transform the lives of the fifty percent of the workforce whose livelihood depended on agriculture. The farm bills were introduced into an agrarian social condition that, since the colonial period, had been dominated by the urban credit markets. The majority small-holding farmers in India have long been engaged in producing crops for geographically distant and unknown markets, with no control over the prices of their products. Therefore, state support, farm subsidies, and protections from market forces were essential for small and middle holding farmers to sustain their livelihoods.

The farm bill threatened the already precarious living conditions of the farmers, exacerbated by credit network exploitation and a global

farm price crisis. Consequently, the bills invited widespread opposition. Farmers from northern and northwestern India began to march towards Delhi. The year-long protest movement against the new legislation had its beginning in the western Indian states of Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan. By the end of October 2020, the farmers marched towards Delhi. On 7 November 2020, the farmers' organisations formed the *Samyukt Kisan Morcha*. Due to police restrictions, the farmers set up protest camps on the highways bordering Delhi. These protest sites became spaces for daily protests, organised by farmers' collectives and joined by activists and intellectuals. The movement continued for a year, transforming the highway borders of Delhi into venues for revolutionary poems, speeches, and reading of literature connected to mass movements.

These farm bills were reform efforts by an elite ruling stratum, a social group with limited interactions with villages and farmers. Farmers, particularly those engaged in cash crop cultivation, have been experiencing a deeper crisis due to the high cost of production and fluctuating prices for their products. The protesting farmers considered the farm bill as an intensified neoliberal onslaught on agrarian landscapes and livelihoods already ravaged by the industrialization of agriculture. However, the farmers' protest also became a focal point for politically motivated opportunities and controversies. Perceiving this movement predominantly through an electoral political lens tends to limit the widening possibility of locating the farmers' protest as an integral part of the global scale 'right to nature' movements. Agriculture as a way of life has been facing multidimensional crises, especially in regions that experienced the Green Revolution intensely. The logic of neoliberal capitalism makes grand claims that only technology-oriented capital-intensive restructuring of agricultural production can solve the crisis. However, this agroecological restructuring under capitalism is driven by an endless drive to make nature a cheap commodity that can be circulated globally. Capital's relentless search for new avenues of accumulation manifests globally in the form of agro-ecological reforms.

In response to the year-long protest, the Government of India repealed the farm bills in 2021.

The farmers' movement for their agricultural autonomy represents a struggle against the reproduction of mercantile dominance in

agriculture. Corporate control over the landscape is strategized through large-scale environment-making programmes, especially mega-infrastructure development projects and the development of large-scale mono-crop plantations. Both these processes transform the biosphere into exchangeable commodities. Capitalism projects the massive appropriation of nature as saleable commodities as a solution to crisis and poverty. However, the new language of justice evolved through the framers' movements challenges capitalism's claims of projecting 'land grab' as the best way to addressing crisis and to create new jobs. The officials presented the farm bills as a solution to the agricultural crisis in India. However, farmers countered that these Farm Bills would intensify corporate land grabs. This article examines these deeply interconnected issues and argues that the Delhi farmers' movement requires the language of an environmental justice movement to fully recognize farmers' agency in mobilizing radical resistance against legislations that are aimed at introducing major agro-ecological reforms without achieving substantive socio-economic equality.

The Regulation of Agricultural Marketing: Colonial and Post-Colonial Histories

Modern Agriculture in its broad definition includes farming, processing, transportation, selling as well as the use of tools, machinery and fertiliser. Coordination of these activities gives advantage to the capitalists to generate profit. During the colonial period, significant intervention was made in agriculture by the governments transforming the subcontinent into a kitchen garden for the industrial world. As Richard Levins and Richard Lewontin observed "The chief consequence of technological innovation to increase on-farm productivity has been to make on-farm productivity less and less important in determining agricultural value."¹ The industrialization of farming led to the emergence of a powerful class of rural bourgeois in villages with strong ties to urban markets. They disregarded and considered uncultivated fields such as forests, wetlands, coasts, riverbeds, mangroves, and grasslands as wastelands. Colonial policies aimed to transform natural landscapes into agricultural fields, homogenizing nature in the process. This process was accompanied and facilitated by intensified state control over agricultural activities. The colonial state introduced a managerial

¹ Richard Levins and Richard Lewontin, *The Dialectical Biologist* (Harvard: Harvard University Press, 1985), 213.

view of agriculture to attempt to facilitate colonial capital for greater control over agricultural production.

The history of India's institutional framework for agricultural marketing can be traced back to the Royal Commission on Agriculture, in 1928. Chaired by Lord Linlithgow, the Commission examined the condition of agriculture and recommended a range of institutional, technological, and scientific interventions required for an "increase in the pace of agricultural progress" in India.² This reflected the colonial state's post-World War I preference to promote industrial appropriation of natural riches. Emphasizing the significance of marketing, the Commission stressed the need to transform agriculture into a profitable enterprise. It essentially recommended an intensification of the ongoing process of linking the South Asian rural economy to a network of commodity markets. Subsequently, the Government of India established the office of the Agricultural Marketing Advisor in 1935. The increasing dominance of market requirements in agriculture, especially in the production of food crops, transformed the social dynamics of the rural world. Cities began to establish their dominance in the form of agricultural markets. Urban demand for natural riches in the form of food, raw materials and energy sources started converting every possible inch of land into resource bases. The increasing urban control eliminates the collective rights on commons and privatized natural resources.

The colonial interventions pushed agricultural production and distribution increasingly into the domain of engineers, scientists, and policy makers. Colonial capitalism promoted the one-dimensional perception of considering landforms as spaces for large plantations to cultivate exportable crops. The Royal Commission on Agriculture (1928) observed that "serious obstacle to agricultural improvement is, in some provinces, caused by the subdivision and fragmentation of holdings. Subdivision is chiefly due to the laws of inheritance customary amongst Hindus and Muhammadans which enjoys a succession to immovable property amongst all the heirs."³ Establishing market control over the rural world dispossessed smallholders and those who depended on forests and common lands for survival. Thus, food became a commodity that had to be purchased. Farmers, fishers, and pastoralists lost their sovereignty to access food and energy resources. Consequently, food

² "Royal Commission on Agriculture in India: Report," *Government of India* (Bombay: Government Central Press, 1928), 4.

³ "Royal Commission on Agriculture in India: Report," *Government of India*, 14.

shortage was one of the major aftereffects of the one and half century-long colonial rule in South Asia.

The policy of adopting a commodity production-centered approach to transforming the rural world continued in India even after the end of British colonial rule in 1947. One of the primary objectives of the state-led development programmes called the Five-Year Plans, stressed food self-sufficiency. The first Five Year Plan (1951-56) aimed to address the issue of poverty by focusing on enhancing agricultural production. However, the Plan Proposal of the first Five Year Plan endorsed the economic goal of increased production as its central aim.⁴ This was equally a process of establishing bureaucratic domination in the village agricultural production center by controlling the development of irrigation and power infrastructures and the supply of seeds and fertilizers. The intensified bureaucratic control accelerated capitalistic control over agricultural production. As argued by Francine R. Frankel, the result of setting the economic goal of increased production “was an approach to planning that limited the government’s role to the creation of social capital and financial incentives for the expansion of private enterprises.”⁵

The First Five-Year Plan proposal observed:

Uneconomic holdings are at the root of many of the difficulties of Indian agriculture. With the growing pressure on land, their number is increasing. Agriculture cannot be developed as an efficient industry unless the unit of management becomes much larger than it is at present. It is true that where agriculture does not require much investment, natural conditions are favourable and the cultivators are skillful and industrious, small holdings may produce even higher yields per acre than large holdings. The problem in India, as in many other under-developed countries, is however, a much larger one. The major factors for securing increase in production are the application on a wide scale of scientific knowledge and increased capital investment in its different forms. These factors can be employed only if agriculture is organised on the basis of relatively larger units of management

⁴ “The First Year Plan: A Draft Outline (1951),” *Government of India Planning Commission - Part III*, 73.

⁵ Francine R Frankel, *India’s Political Economy (1947-2004)*, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006), 86.

and production than the existing holdings. Such larger units have undoubted advantages. In a farm of substantial size, it is possible to eliminate several wasteful operations, and to ensure better planning of the use of land, including selection of crops, rotation and soil conservation, development of irrigation and introduction of improved agricultural techniques. Economies which are not available to small farms are available to large ones. By its very nature a larger unit of management can secure more credit and finance and can apply these to greater advantage, can diversify its economy and can make a relatively greater contribution to the solution of the country's food problem.⁶

Sukhamoy Chakravarty, an expert in planned economic development, argued that “in the early 1950s, when the planning process was initiated in India, there was a general consensus on a ‘commodity centred approach.’” (Chakravarty, 1987) While promising millions of poverty-stricken villagers hopes to achieve better life, the Five Year-Plan did not propose any significant measures to eliminate landlordism or to have concrete measures to achieve substantive equality in a rapidly industrialising agricultural world. Consequently, in the early decades of independence, the Indian agricultural sector experienced the development of capitalism without major changes in the existing landlordism.

The industrialisation of agriculture required the development of irrigation networks and the application of chemical fertilisers. The use of chemical fertilisers enabled capitalist farmers to extract soil nutrients as commodities for a geographically distant market. As Marx observed the industrialisation of agriculture “disturbs the metabolic interaction between man and earth, i.e. it prevents the return to the soil of its constituent elements consumed by man in the form of food and clothing; hence it hinders the operation of the eternal natural condition for the lasting fertility of the soil.”⁷ The application of technology in agricultural production increased farmers' dependence on the urban market.

Small holding and marginal farmers, those who engaged in subsistence farming lost their autonomy to practice horticulture as

⁶ “The First Year Plan: A Draft Outline (1951),” *Government of India Planning Commission - Part III*, 97-98.

⁷ Karl Marx, *Capital Vol. 1* (London: Penguin, 1976), 637.

a way of organising their livelihood. Moreover, capital intensive agriculture enabled the landlord class to accumulate landed property by dispossessing smallholding peasants. As Marx aptly observed, “in the sphere of agriculture, large-scale industry has a more revolutionary effect than elsewhere, for the reason that it annihilates the bulwark of the old society, the ‘peasant’, and substitutes for him the wage-labourer.”⁸ The Zamindari Abolition Acts and Tenancy Acts passed in various Indian states in the 1950s did not provide land to the landless or marginal peasants. Consequently, capitalist agricultural development did not lead to any increased overall welfare of the rural masses.

The advent of capitalist agricultural development during the 1960s and 1970s made marketing strategies a major concern for the state and capitalists. The introduction of high yield Borlaug seed-fertiliser wheat technology was a revolutionary breakthrough in the food grain production sector. However, the surge in increased agricultural production necessitated institutional and infrastructural developments to maximise profit generation. States adopted schemes to subsidise cultivation by providing aids to invest in small scale irrigation works like wells, tanks, and pump sets.

At the same time, the idea of total takeover of agricultural produce by the state was a prominent idea after the end of colonialism. The aim was to ensure market efficiency while balancing distributive justice in favour of the farmers.⁹ Regulating food grain prices for urban factory workers was crucial for supporting industrial development. In India, state regulation of marketing was an imperative, particularly in the immediate post-colonial decades, due to significant food grain shortages. A major turning point in state intervention in the marketing of agricultural products occurred in the 1960s with the formulation of the Agricultural Produce Marketing Act (APMC Act). This Act, adopted by state governments, aimed to curb the dominance of middlemen traders. However, the APMCs met with resistance from traders and the representatives of mainstream economic thought, which argued that such acts led to market inefficiencies and fragmentation in distribution networks.

⁸ Karl Marx, *Capital Vol. 1*, 637.

⁹ Zaibun Y Jasdhanwalla, “Efficient Agricultural Marketing.” *Economic and Political Weekly*, vol. 12, no, 53, (1977): 133-140.

The Farm Bills and the Question of Right to Nature

In the early 1990s, the Government of India initiated a series of economic policy reforms aimed at opening up the Indian economy for corporate and foreign capital to make investments in infrastructure, industries, and social service sectors. These reforms also led to the rolling back of several of the social welfare schemes including subsidies for farmers to access electric power, water, and chemical fertilizers. The introduction of neoliberal capitalism further accentuated urban domination over agriculture. The shift towards market-oriented policies led to the emergence of a new wave of powerful social movements in the global south. The intensifying market dependency made the lives of farmers, fishers, pastoralists and indigenous people much more vulnerable to inflation, falling price of agricultural crops, and intensifying natural disasters. Consequently, the issue of socio-environmental justice has become a major concern to define the contemporary social processes.

In 2014, the Government of India considered the possibilities to privatise the public sector Food Corporation of India, an institutional mechanism aimed to provide effective price support to the farmers and to function as an agency for the collection and distribution of food grains. This was a time when the increasing number of farmers' suicide became a major issue in India. After the neoliberal turn of the economy, farmers commit suicide due to crop failure related debt crisis. The ecological consequences of industrial agriculture became an intense issue in terms of loss of biodiversity, disappearance of multiplicity of livelihood patterns, and the depletion of soil fertility. Landlessness remains a major issue in Indian villages. Despite the Green Revolution having been projected as a resounding success, it failed to ensure adequate food access for the impoverished. Instead, the intensified industrialisation of agriculture increased rural inequality and indebtedness. Additionally, the intensified reliance on fertilisers and chemicals progressively reduced soil fertility, painting farmers as "loss makers" under the industrial mode of living.

According to the Agricultural Census of India, 2015-16 86.2 percent of the cultivators have less than 5 acres of land.¹⁰ The average size of landholding in rural India in India in 2015-16 was only 1.08 hectares. The average monthly income of an agricultural household in India,

¹⁰ "All India Report on Agriculture Census," *Department of Agriculture, Cooperation & Farmers Welfare Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare - 2015-16*.

as per the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO), 2012-13 estimate was Rs. 6426. The protesting farmers argued that the new bills further intensify these issues and eliminate their livelihoods and autonomy. In essence, the farm bills had the potential to remove barriers for limitless urbanization of rural labour power. Additionally, it had the necessary potential to establish monopoly control over natural resources in the name of market efficiency.

Nonlinearization of nature is the ideological background of the contemporary interventions in the institutional and legal infrastructures of agriculture. This is clear in the global land deal data provided by the Land Matrix Initiative. According to the ‘landmatrix’ estimate, 109 forestry-related land deals in India in 2022 sold 4,151, 112 hectares of land.¹¹ Such large-scale land deals give corporate capitalists complete control over natural riches. The majority of the people displaced by such large-scale land deals are from poor backgrounds, especially small-holding peasants. There are translational alliances like the Asian Farmers’ Association for Sustainable Rural Development (AFA) to struggle for the rights of people depending on agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and pastoralism for their survival. AFA points out that the major reasons for poverty in Asia included lack of access and control over natural resources, health and education, degraded ecosystems and vulnerabilities in price fluctuations and natural disasters. According to the UNDP’s Global Multidimensional Poverty Index, 2022, nearly 385 million poor people live in South Asia, of which the majority are children, lower castes and people who live in rural areas.¹²

The All India Kisan Sangharsh Coordination Committee (AIKSCC) was formed in 2017 with the aim of addressing the perennial issues of falling agricultural crop prices and farmers indebtedness. According to various field-based reports, between 1995 and 2020, more than 400,000 farmers in India committed suicide due to debt crisis. The glaring disparities in the distribution of agricultural surplus and continuous decline in crop price have led to unprecedented farm crises. It is important to see that since the British colonial period, the agricultural sector majorly depended on credit networks. Farmers engaged in cash crop production sold their products for unknown and geographically

¹¹ “Large-scale land acquisitions in Asia,” *Snapshot*, accessed 25 May 2024 https://landmatrix.org/documents/168/Brochure_LSLAs_Asia_2022.pdf

¹² “Unpacking deprivation bundles to reduce multidimensional poverty,” *UNDP Global Multidimensional Poverty Index, 2022: 2*.

distant urban markets. The farmers' protest addressed the issues of unequal distribution of agricultural surplus, receding the right to access nature as use value. Initiated by less than one thousand farmers, the farm movement has become one of the largest farmers movements in India. The movement had to face major state repression and opposition. Nevertheless, the movement was a remarkable success in terms of attracting global attention. Therefore, it is important to examine the historical and environmental factors that allowed the farmers to gather wider attention.

The decisive participation of women made the farmers movement a case of intersectional environmentalism. Women from the villages of Haryana and Punjab were a visible and active presence in the movement.¹³ The protesting women included lower and middle caste farmers mostly from Punjab and Haryana, a region known for its patriarchal social structure. The newspapers and magazines covered the images of women protesting at Delhi borders. Women with limited access to landownership and resources had been affected by intensified market control over agriculture. Ecofeminist studies in the context of global periphery discussed the issue of invisibilising women's labour. Esther Boserup's study on women in agricultural development in 1970 *Women's Role in Economic Development* illustrated how development affects women's subordinate position in most societies.¹⁴ In the Indian context, Bina Agarwal demonstrated how women in poor rural households are victims of environmental degradation in quite gender-specific ways.¹⁵

However, the environmental history and environmental sociology courses offered by the majority of our universities usually offer a very limited and textbook oriented understanding on the interlinked issues of gender and environment. The challenge of an environmental historian

¹³ Sanskriti Talwar, "How Women Farmers in Punjab Mobilised Against the Farm Law," *BehanBox* accessed 24 May 2024, <https://behanbox.com/2021/01/04/how-women-farmers-in-punjab-mobilised-against-the-farm-laws/> and Mariam Dhawale, "Thousands of Women Lead Protest on Mahila Kisan Divas," *Peasant Struggle* (March-April 2021), 20-27.

¹⁴ Ester Boserup, Su Fei Tan, and Camilla Toulmin, eds., *Woman's Role in Economic Development* (London: Routledge, 2007).

¹⁵ Bina Agarwal, *A Field of One's Own: Gender and Land Rights in south Asia*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1994; Bina Agarwal, "The Gender and Environment Debate: Lessons from India," *Feminist Studies*, vol. 18, no. (1992): 1119-58.

who studies social movements against the capitalist degradation of ecology is to identify a general connecting link to bring together numerous and infinite varieties of social struggles. About 75 percent of women workers in India are farm labourers. However, according to human development surveys, more than 83 percent of cultivable land is owned and inherited by male members of the family. Technology-based and energy-intensive agricultural practices have historically been acting as a force to amplify gender disparity. Consequently, any form of crisis immediately affects women farmers. Therefore, the protesting women refused the state's request to return home.¹⁶

The analytical methods and theoretical perspective required for such studies are different from the earlier Marxist tradition that paid more attention to direct struggles between capital and labour over surplus value production. The social movements including the farmers struggles against destructive consequences of commodification of farmland and agriculture require environmental justice. The bills collectively had the power to remove the legal and institutional barriers that prevented corporate capitalists from establishing their agriculture market networks. Currently, the poor village woman has the option to take her produce to village Mandi that is controlled by a state institutional structure. Elimination of the Mandi would completely take away a women farmer's right to engage in farm production. This is crucial to sufficiently acknowledge the role of women and other marginalized social section in framing the language of social protests. Referring to such instances intersectional environmentalist Leah Thomas observed that "bringing in social justice into environmental programs is some capacity is really important."¹⁷

'The declaration of the rights of peasants' passed by the United Nation's Human Rights Council provides a crucial framework to locate the farmers movements within the larger frame of the right to nature movements. It observes that "peasants and other people working in rural

¹⁶ Amil Bhatnagar, "Women Take the Lead at Singhu, Say There is No Question of Going Back," *The Indian Express* (19 Jan. 2021), accessed 22 May 2022, <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/delhi/women-take-the-lead-at-singhu-say-there-is-no-question-of-going-back-7151801/>

¹⁷ Sophie Capshaw-Mack, "A Conversation with Leah Thomas, Intersectional Environmentalist," *State of the Planet*, 10 November 2021, accessed 19 March 2023, <https://news.climate.columbia.edu/2021/11/10/a-conversation-with-leah-thomas-intersectional-environmentalist/>

areas have the right to food sovereignty. Food sovereignty is the right of peoples to healthy and culturally appropriate food produced through socially just and ecologically sensitive methods. It entails people's right to participate in decision-making and to define their own food and agricultural systems."¹⁸ The powerful and globally interconnected right to food movements made it imperative for the UN to draft this resolution. The 'right to food' or 'food sovereignty movements' had the potential to challenge elite environmentalism that focuses on the language of conservation. The food sovereignty concept stands for farmer right to decide what to cultivate and what to do with their crops.

Grassroots organizations of peasant, tribal and women's movements in the recent decades, especially after the economic liberalization in the 1990s, actively come together to form national-level platforms such as the All-India Kisan Sabha, and All India Democratic Women's Association. The immanent tendency of neoliberal capitalism to exhaust nature as well as the biological limits of workers shape the socio-economic experiences, rendering them inherently violent in peripheral countries. As per the estimate of the National Crime Records Bureau under the union Home Ministry of the Government of India, nearly four lakh farmers in India were forced to commit suicide between 1995 and 2020. The primary reason for farmers suicide is indebtedness and exploitation. Farming as a human intervention in nature converts nutrients as food to meet human survival sufficiency. However, agriculture has always been a medium in human societies to exploit the labour power of others. The farmers movement against the three farm bills passed by the Government argued that they would promote corporate profiteering and black-marketing. The concern and demands of the farmers' movements were thus in alignment with the global right to nature movements, especially the voice of poor women, elderly farmers, and landless agricultural workers.

Bibliography

- Agarwal, Bina. "The Gender and Environment Debate: Lessons from India," *Feminist Studies* 18, no. 1 (1992): 119-58.
- Agarwal, Bina. *A Field of One's Own: Gender and Land Rights in south Asia*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1994.

¹⁸ *The State of food and Agriculture*. Food and Agricultural Organization – 2005, accessed 25 May 2024, <https://www.fao.org/4/a0050e/a0050e08.htm#:~:text=Food%20sovereignty%20is%20the%20right,dumping%20of%20products%20in%20their>

- Bhatnagar, Amil, “Women Take the Lead at Singhu, Say There is No Question of Going Back.” *The Indian Express*. 19 Jan, 2021. Accessed 22 May 2022. <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/delhi/women-take-the-lead-at-singhu-say-there-is-no-question-of-going-back-7151801/>
- Boserup, Ester, Su Fei Tan, and Camilla Toulmin, Eds. *Woman’s Role in Economic Development*. London: Routledge, 2007.
- Capshaw-Mack, Sophie. “A Conversation with Leah Thomas, Intersectional Environmentalist.” *State of the Planet*, 10 November 2021, Accessed 19 March 2023. <https://news.climate.columbia.edu/2021/11/10/a-conversation-with-leah-thomas-intersectional-environmentalist/>
- Chakravarty, Sukhamoy. *Development Planning: The Indian Experience*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1987.
- “All India Report on Agriculture Census,” *Department of Agriculture, Cooperation & Farmers Welfare Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare 2015-16*.
- Dhawale, Mariam. “Thousands of Women Lead Protest on Mahila Kisan Divas.” *Peasant Struggle (March-April 2021)*.
- The State of food and Agriculture*. Food and Agricultural Organization – 2005. Accessed 25 May 2024. <https://www.fao.org/4/a0050e/a0050e08.htm#:~:text=Food%20sovereignty%20is%20the%20right,dumping%20of%20products%20in%20their>
- Frankel, Francine R. *India’s Political Economy (1947-2004)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006.
- Royal Commission on Agriculture in India: Report,” *Government of India*. Bombay: Government Central Press, 1928.
- “The First Year Plan: A Draft Outline (1951).” *Government of India Planning Commission - Part III*, 73.
- Jasdanwalla, Zaibun Y. “Efficient Agricultural Marketing.” *Economic and Political Weekly*. vol. 12, no, 53, (1977): 133-140.
- “Large-scale land acquisitions in Asia,” *Snapshot*, accessed 25 May 2024 https://landmatrix.org/documents/168/Brochure_LSLAs_Asia_2022.pdf
- Levins, Richard and Richard Lewontin. *The Dialectical Biologist*. Harvard: Harvard University Press, 1985.
- Marx, Karl. *Capital Vol. 1*. London: Penguin, 1976.
- Talwar, Sanskriti. “How Women Farmers in Punjab Mobilised Against the Farm Law.” *BehanBox*. accessed 24 May 2024. <https://behanbox.com/2021/01/04/how-women-farmers-in-punjab-mobilised-against-the-farm-laws/>

DYNAMICS OF SOCIALISATION OF SHADOWED FAIR SEX: HISTORIC INITIATIVES OF BREKLUM MISSION IN KORAPUT

- Raghumani Naik*

Abstract

The Koraput district in South Odisha is known as “Nature Lovers’ Paradise” because of the area’s immense natural beauty, variety of flora and fauna, and blissful comfort provided by the verdant surroundings. The Dalit folks and the colourful adivasis live there naturally. Because of the steep mountains, rift valleys, swift waterfalls, and thick forests, the area was inaccessible. This is the reason this area stayed backward and undeveloped for ages, being cut off from the rest of the world. People’s literacy was appalling. Because education was viewed as “unbecoming of the modesty of the women,” it was a dystopia for women. The occupations of the women were limited to the home and hearth. They were seen as little more than fun activities for men. Thus, Koraput was experiencing a “Dark Age” for the women living in this remote area. On May 15, 1882 A.D., the German Breklum Mission arrived in Koraput, marking a turning point in the history of women’s education in this region. To enhance the education of the women in this region, it set up schools, boarding homes, hostels, Bible women’s classes, and theological college, and introduced the Zenana system and Deaconess.

Keywords: Breklum Mission, Women, Schools, Boarding homes, Theological Seminary.

Introduction

Women have always been subjected to irrational male rule. This is a global issue that needs to be addressed. According to Levi Strauss’s “opposition in binary” theory, women have been demoted to a secondary role in the socio-political and economic hierarchy, allowing

* Dr. Raghumani Naik is an Associate Professor in the Department of History at Sambalpur University.

men to hold the top spot. Undoubtedly, the feminist voice has opposed the Straussian notion of hierarchy, but it has not received the anticipated response. The fate of the women of United Koraput was the same as that of women worldwide. The extreme poverty, ignorance, and terrible health conditions of the tribal women - and women in general - in this region of Odisha, however, were even more upsetting.

It will be in the fitness of things to shed light on the position of women in Odisha, especially in the undivided Koraput district, on the eve of the Breklum Mission in 1882. It was in a precarious condition. They did not have any social identity.

Nor were they able to come out of their daily routine-bound lives. They were considered enjoyable things and machines for producing children, rearing them, and maintaining household work from dawn to dusk. They were prohibited from learning because of a belief that attainment of knowledge would become ‘**unbecoming of the modesty of the women.**’¹ They were hobbled by a number of superstitions and social norms. It was a part of their chore to collect forest products and sell them in the daily markets, rear cattle, and do agricultural as well as manual work as laborers for the upkeep of their family. They played an important role in the tribal economy. On the other hand, the Dalit women were doing small business, daily wagering, manual work, etc. for the subsistence of their families. Besides these compulsions, what used to mar their lives were social evils like infanticide, child marriage, the celibacy of widowhood, and the practice of polygamy in society. The German Breklum Mission arrived in Koraput and offered women there a glimmer of hope during this unfavorable time. It required some audacious actions to breach the conventional barrier. Against the backdrop of the infamous “Dark Age,” a new era emerged.

Advent of Breklum Mission to Koraput and Thereafter

The Rev. Christian Jensen, a Pietist from Breklum in northern West Germany, was the driving force behind the founding of the Breklum Mission on September 19, 1876 A.D.² He established a home mission

¹ B.C. Padhi, *Socio-Economic Conditions of Tribals under the British Rule (1803–1936)* (Kolkata: Punthi Pustak, 1992), 166.

² N. Samantroy, “History of Odia Literature (1803–1920),” *Cuttack*, (1964): 45–47.

to generate missionaries known as ‘Brekhum Mission Seminary’ on April 10, 1877 A.D. He made the workers of the mission well-versed in the Biblical gospels and the words of Christ so that these prospective missionaries would send forth Christianity across the dark world where enlightenment had never cast its ray.³ Rev. Ernst Pohl and Rev. Harmann Bothmann were the pioneer missionaries to Koraput.

Nature and Scope of the Study

Through increased missionary activity, the mission sought (1882 A.D. to 1978 A.D.) to better the men and women of this underserved area. Nonetheless, the women in this district continued to lag behind in terms of social status and education due to utter neglect. Thus, in this research study, the scholar aims to shed light on the importance of the mission and the heroic measures taken to enhance their education and social standing.

Research Methodology

For this article, the library documentation approach was used with an empirical and historical viewpoint. Pragmatic data was also investigated. The current effort has employed descriptive methodologies from an analytical and historical standpoint. For gathering pertinent information, a simple random sample, close-ended oral inquiry, and a questionnaire were utilized.

Data Collection

This piece of work has been written using both primary and secondary data. In addition, interviews were conducted with former and current bishops, pastors, catechumens, preachers, gurus, church personnel such as secretaries and staff, and, most importantly, accounts left behind by the missionaries themselves. Archival materials are taken into consideration for the current study, including journals, magazines, chronicles, periodicals, souvenirs, gazetteers, newspapers, letters, books, articles, internet archives, e-books, etc. This article is from the contemporary era, and no inscriptions, numismatics, or ancient materials are available.

³ Bhaskar Das, Social and Economic Life of South Orissa, *Punthi Pustak Cuttack*, (1985):155-157.

Findings

The Breklum Mission has done an amazing job raising health awareness among the Koraput tribal people. From self-immolation to prayer, polytheism to monotheism, and from reverence for the natural world to Jesus Christ, it evolved. People who were completely dependent on traditional healers such as Gurumain, Disari, Shaman, magic, spells, exorcists, and sorcery and were losing their precious lives as a result of not receiving treatment, abandoned traditional medicine in favour of modern medicine. Along with other services including clinics, dispensaries, leprosy havens, and mobile health care systems, the mission constructed hospitals such as the Ebenezer Hospital at Kotpad, Christian Hospital at Nabarangpur, Bissam Cuttack Hospital at Bissam Cuttack, and Navajeevan Based Hospital at Doliambo. It was a malaria-prone area, and the Breklum mission helped get rid of the disease by taking the required measures. The women and children of this hilly district are no longer exploited and ignored by males in society. They are now availing themselves of all the opportunities they deserve. It was possible only with the yeoman service of the mission.

The Tribal Way of Health Treatment and the Mission's Role in Health Care

Mission's Manuring at the Root

It was the well-proven realization of the mission that, sans progress in the field of education, other developments were out of the question. So, it took up the work from the point where it needed to be started. The mission decided to impart both Biblical knowledge, general education, and religious knowledge to women to make them fit for society and the development of their mental and spiritual lives. Because the mission realized that a nation's development is closely associated with the educational development of its women, the Gospel of God would not reach the houses. Women are an integral part of society, and they also make equal contributions to promoting social harmony.

First, Christian women were given education by the mission. Through teaching them the Bible, great care was taken to ensure that they could read and write with efficiency. For example, as early as 1893 A.D., Johannes Timm's wife began instructing ladies in Bible stories.⁴ The wives of

⁴ J. Timm, "Ist Quarterly Report," Trans. by A. Asha (Jeypore, 1893), 12.

Rev. Timm and Rev. Gloyer were a companionable teaching resource for the women folk. The seminary took it as its own responsibility to provide special training for those women who were found competent in reading and writing so that they could become teachers in ministry. Indeed, Rev. Gloyer was looking for a few ladies who would assist in gospel preaching and receive training. Second, the missionaries in Koraput informed the Breklum Mission leadership about the Jeypore Estate's deaconess requirement. In order to oversee and expedite the mission, two groups of missionaries, consisting of two members each, were dispatched to Koraput in 1905 and 1909, respectively. A deacon oversaw the Christian hospital; another oversaw the boarding school for girls and the teaching of ladies in the Bible. The third was in charge of the job done by the local ladies. At Kotpad, the trio was positioned. In the town of Jeypore, the fourth started working as a zenana.⁵

The wives of missionaries took an interest in providing education to non-Christian women because the missionaries were denied access to these women. For example, with orthodoxy being an inseparable part of life, non-Christian women had no scope for going outside their houses. Therefore, special training was given to Christian women so that they could interact effectively with them. Knowledge of theology was given to the wives of seminary students. Mrs. Speck, who knew Odia, was a nice choice as a teacher for the native learners. The women were to be instructed by Mrs. Gloyer. For this reason, missionary wives were also enrolling in camps. When their wives were interacting with the women, the missionaries would preach to men. This kind of unity had a major role in spreading the gospel among the populace. Throughout her husband's camp, Mrs. Leuckfeld taught the women and was by his side constantly.⁶

The deaconess who used to oversee it was assisted by women missionaries stationed in the town districts. They used to preach the gospel to non-Christian women when they visited. Rev. W. Ahrens' sister maintained constant communication with the Muslim women she shared the gospel with. Consequently, via this form of one-on-one interaction, many non-Christian families were converted to Christianity.

⁵ R. Tauscher, "Nutano Sambado," *Christian Mitra* 3 (Koraput, 1935), 3.

⁶ Tauscher, 3.

Later, the mission decided to start providing education for the women in this area. As a result, it required a variety of actions to teach them, primarily the skills of reading, writing, and listening. Thus, the mission began in the following manner:

i. Establishment of Girls Schools

Girls were not permitted to enroll in co-educational programmes or attend schools. There was a noticeable shift and advancement in southern Odisha's educational system after 1871 A.D. There were no girls enrolled in school in this district prior to 1873-1874 A.D.⁷ In light of this, Breklum Mission showed commendable initiative by establishing schools for the girls living in this area.

ii. Establishment of Co-Boarding Homes

The main locations for educational activity were either orphanages or boarding houses. From the outset, the mission established boarding homes in each of its mission locations. It set up boarding homes for boys and girls to give orphaned and impoverished, despairing, and defenseless pupils free housing and education. In addition, boarding house kids from remote areas without access to a primary or upper elementary school were housed there in exchange for a little boarding charge from their parents. The local missionary, who had the authority to retain the prisoners in the boarding house, was typically the primary authority of the boarding home.

The boarding home's residents were required to abide by the rules. The monthly boarding charge for the prisoners' parents was eight annas or 0.50 rupees. Such costs were due to the boarding authorities from the church for the most impoverished inmates. In the event a student at a higher elementary or high school dropped a class because she was too lazy, her parents would be responsible for covering the additional cost of her board.

Important Boarding Houses were:

One boy and 27 girls were living in the Koraput Boarding Home in 1888 A.D., but the population quickly grew to 58 boys and 27 girls.

⁷ Report of the Indian Education Commission 1882, *Government of India* Vol. J. (3 Feb, 1882): 15.

From 1899 until 1914, Mrs. Timmcke served as the boarding home's housemother.

When Kotpad Boarding Homes (for boys and girls) first opened in 1891, there were seven children living there. By 1896–1897, there were thirteen. It was dubbed the “School of Boarding and Care.”

Doliambo Boarding Home (Boys and Girls)

Laxmipur Boarding Home (Boys and Girls)

So, the Breklum Mission was the forerunner of co-education in this isolated district before independence.

Boarding homes came into existence for two primary reasons. Orphans were accommodated there, and the children in rural areas got the opportunity to get an education where there were no educational opportunities for the girls' students. In these boarding homes, students received secular education, spiritual counseling, and career training. By being together and sharing meals, they were also overcoming the division of castes. Still, many boarding orphan girls married well-educated, converted Christians. Above all, the mission gave stipends to girls who wanted to pursue higher education.

iii. Establishment of Day Boardings

The mission managed day boarding in all small stations and mission settlements in addition to boarding houses. The midday meal programmes of today, which promote both school attendance and child nutrition, were similar to the boarding home days. These were referred to as “boarding” in India, but “Kosthauser” in the mission reports.

iv. Theological Seminary and Spiritual Knowledge to Women

Christian women's education was the mission's initial action. In the theological seminary, those who met the requirements to read and write were given specialized training for their future roles in the church's ministry. The seminary was founded in Kotpad in 1896 A.D. with the intention of teaching men and women alike spiritual knowledge. The wives of the seminary students received theological instruction as well. In Odia, Mrs. Speck was a young and seasoned educator who worked with women in the seminary.

v. Introduction of Zenana or Senana System

The mission introduced an innovative system known as the Zenana or Senana system for housekeeping women. Informal training was given to the middle and upper classes' women in the art of home management. The non-Christian women were constantly inside their homes, giving the missionaries less opportunity to speak with them face-to-face during their preaching time. Christian ladies received specialized training on how to interact with non-Christian women. In spite of this, the mission assigned one of the deaconesses to work as a zenana in the Jeypore town. The deaconess was assisted by a few missionary wives. A door-to-door campaign was launched. The result was excellent.

The sister of Rev. W. Ahrens had gained popularity among Muslim women. She could talk to them about Christ and his teachings. Consequently, many non-Christian women were brought into Christianity. Sunday schools were also organized to provide education to adults and housewives. The task of educating rural, uneducated, and non-Christian women under this system fell to lady missionaries.

vi. The Establishment of Girls' Hostels

Mrs. Timm established a dormitory for girls at Kotpad in 1901 A.D. with 16 girls. A girls' school was constructed in 1904 A.D. not far from the hostel grounds. In 1906 A.D., there were 100 girls, and in 1913 A.D., there were 125. The girls' Upper School in Kotpad was renovated to a Middle English school, and a primary school for girls was established there. A new school building was built in 1927 A.D, with the help of 104 girl students.⁸

Year	No. of Students
1932	367
1933	441
1934	353

This large percentage of girls' attendance increased because of the establishment of girls' boarding homes and the girls' school at Kotpad. Female education in Kotpad reached new heights thanks to the efforts

⁸ Otto Waack, *Church and Mission in India, Vol. 1 (1876-1914)* (Delhi: ISPCK, 1997), 517-18.

of American Missionary Agatha Tatge. This made it possible for Otty Jessen and Mathilde Jespersen, the two deaconesses, to continue the work that Agathe had left behind. However, because of their incompatibility with the missionaries, these two deaconesses were forced to leave India. From that point on, R. Speck assumed leadership of this institution. Following the departure of the two deaconesses from India due to disagreements with the missionaries and mission boards, this school came under the administration of the station missionaries, Revs. Gloyer, Meyer and R. Speck.

vii. Bible Class for Women

The girls in the seminary began receiving regular Bible instruction. Some women and girls in their different areas were educated by the spouses of Rev. Timm and Rev. Gloyer. As early as 1893 A.D., Johannes Timm's wife, for instance, would tell women stories from the Bible. The women were eager to pick up knowledge from the missionaries. Furthermore, the mission introduced a women's Bible class by 1954 A.D., and ten women were admitted into the seminary. Each of them was given rupees seventeen as a stipend. It was for the first time that the seminary trained full-time 'Bible women.' Of course, short courses of training were given to some interested women at different times.

To instruct the Bible women, a request was made to the 'Danish Mission Society' to send a lady missionary. During their training period, as Tauscher writes, they had to go to preaching camps in the villages. After completion of the Bible women's training, they were deputed to the Deanery headquarters, where they organized women's fellowship groups, taught Sunday school girls and confirmation students, and visited the parish centre to instruct women⁹ Even today, in every deanery, there is a Bible woman working actively among Christian and non-Christian women.

viii. Role of Church Council and Synod for the Development of Women's Education

The synod and church councils trained women for future roles in the church's mission. It was discovered that the only way to approach non-

⁹ *Church Council, Kotpad, 3rd Session Resolution No. 9/3 (11th-13th November, 1953): 2.*

Christian women was through women. As a result, women's growth received a lot of attention, both in terms of education and spirituality.

In 1942 the Synod made the following resolutions:

There ought to be more girls placed in boarding homes. Young females should be thoroughly familiar with the Bible throughout confirmation class. It is important to give working wives the right training. At the major pastoral stations, the daughters of workers should get appropriate guidance prior to marriage. The Bible and hymn books should be a source of encouragement for the married pair. Every parish centre and deanery would establish a women's group. (SIC). Till 1947, no woman was a member of any of the congregational councils. So, the Kotpad Panchayat suggested that two women would be selected as representatives of the Synod. Since then, women have been represented in the synod.

ix. Establishment of Women's Fellowship Groups

Women fellowship groups also visited nearby villages to preach the gospel, and along with that, they gave special instructions on hygiene, childcare, and nutrition. Finally, it came to a stage where instructing women became a priority, and importance was given to it in the congregation. It was decided in the Church Council that wives of gurus and pastors should teach the women of their respective villages.

x. Steps for Intellectual Growth and Women's Freedom

The objective of the mission was to make them sensible, moral, industrious, and pious young women. It aimed to make them good wives for the native Christians. So, it introduced such measures for them. Women's leadership training was organized for the wives of pastors and evangelists. Bible women were trained in the seminary and deployed for evangelistic work among the women. Girls were taught housework like sewing, knitting, and basket-making and spinning to earn their livelihood. The Church Council also decided to involve women in the election process of the Synod and other missionary activities.

xi. Bissam Cuttack Christian Hospital and Training Courses for Women

Christian Hospital of Bissam Cuttack started a school of nursing under the leadership of Mrs. Nancy Henry. It launched a two-year ANM

training programme and a three-year GNM training programme. It was meant to train nurses for CHB itself. This training was mostly given on a subsidy and concession basis. Each year, 10 ANM and 20 GNM took admission and had to pay a minimum price (7-8 thousand only). After passing out, they had to serve this institution for 2 years on a stipend basis, and thereafter they got regular appointments. The hospital provided training, boarding, and lodging free of charge to girls from poor families.¹⁰

Conclusion

True development is always holistic by nature. Being learned and farsighted, the missionaries planned for the all-round development of the tribal women and children. Mere financial support would not have brought about a change in them. Therefore, they first spotted all the weak areas and then took action to improve them. As a result, at present, studying in a mission school is an option available to many Christian women who work outside the church and provide services. In a culture controlled by men, women are no longer seen as delightful objects for men. Instead, they enjoy the same chances and benefits as men and share the same status. The Breklum Mission brought golden days to the women who had been groveling in darkness. The mission pioneered the movement for women's education, which was a noble step. It was through education that the women of this area came to realize the importance of their position.

By initiating measures to enlighten the women, the mission brought into the limelight the issue of Indian women for public debate and discussion and thereby facilitated a change in the indigenous attitude towards the status of women. It resulted in various reformist legislation and the beginning of a new movement for the emancipation of women. The women Christian missionaries used to visit the women of high caste and have comprehensive discussions regarding education, health, and personal development.

Following the mission's initiative, a number of Christian women are associated with religious and social activities in the capacity of pastors, preachers, and secretaries of the women's association. They

¹⁰ "Golden Jubilee Souvenir," *Christian Hospital Bissam Cuttack* (1954–2004): 14.

mark their presence in social work, the eradication of HIV/AIDS, and female awareness programmes. Now they have organized a Women's Desk at Jeypore Central Office to address various problems related to women. A Christian widows' ashram was also established to care for such (achhyut) ladies who were neglected by their respective families. In 1909 A.D., the deaconess Hermine Knuth came to Jeypore and took care of the 'Out Castes Asylum.' She treated patients in her home, visited many houses, and taught women of high caste. In the changing scenario, they are no longer considered inferior to men, nor are they confined within four walls. They take part in every socio-political, cultural, and religious activity of society and can manage themselves without depending on the male members either in the family or outside the family.

Bibliography

- Padhi, B.C. "Socio-Economic Conditions of Tribals under the British Rule (1803-1936)," (Calcutta: Punthi Pustak, 1992).
- Samantroy, N. "History of Odia Literature (1803-1920)," *Cuttack*, (Vidya Bharati, 1964): 45- 47.
- Das, Bhaskar. "Social and Economic Life of South Orissa," *Cuttack* (Punthi Pustak, 1985), 155-157.
- Timm, J. "Ist Quarterly Report," Trans. by A. Asha, Koraput (JELC Press, 1893), 12.
- Tauscher, Rudlof, "Nutano Sambado," Christian Mitra, Third issue, Koraput, Jeypore (JELC Press, 1935), 3.
- "Report of the Indian Education Commission," Vol. J, p. 11 (A.S.O.B.77-T.N.A., 3rd February (Visakhapatnam, 1882), 15.
- Waack, Otto "Church and Mission in India, Vol. 1 (1876-1914)," Delhi: ISPCK, Kashmere Gate, 1997): 517-18.
- Church Council, 3rd Session Resolution No. 9 (3) 11th-13th November, Kotpad (Church Press, 1953), 2.
- "Golden Jubilee Souvenir Christian Hospital Bissam Cuttack (1954-2004)," Koraput (JELC Press, Jeypore, 2004): 14.

RESURRECTED BODY – THOMISTIC RE-READING ON ARISTOTLE’S BODY-SOUL RELATION: A NEW PERSPECTIVE

- Gasper K. J.*

Abstract

“Resurrected Body - Thomistic Re-reading on Aristotle’s Body-Soul Relation: A New Perspective” is a study about the re-reading of St. Thomas Aquinas on Aristotle’s concept of body-soul relation. To attain this purpose the paper tries to expose in the light of the philosophy of Aquinas how ‘body’ is both an exigency in its hylo-morphic constitution as substance and loci for the living principle i.e. form in its various modes of lived- experience of human existence. The primary concern of this study is to show how the question of body as it is explained in the philosophy of a medieval thinker who was widely known as a theologian, but a philosopher as well opens up new ways of thought about theorizing on the body. This essay first explains Aristotle’s views on the soul-body relation. Then it describes Aquinas’s ideas about the same. By examining the philosophy of Aquinas vis-à-vis the body it tries to further explain some underdeveloped aspects of his philosophy on the body. For this purpose, this study applies a theological notion-resurrection - for the detailing of the theme of the essay.

Key Words: Aristotle, Aquinas, body-soul relation, resurrected body, substance

Introduction

This study focuses its attention on the re-reading of St. Thomas Aquinas on Aristotle’s concept of body-soul relation. It tries to expose in the light of the philosophy of Aquinas how ‘body’ is both an exigency in its *hylo-morphic* constitution as substance and loci for the living principle i.e. form in its various modes of lived- experience. The objective of this study is to show how the question of body as it is explained in the philosophy of a medieval thinker who was widely known as a

* Dr. Fr. Gasper K. J. is a Catholic Priest of the Diocese of Cochin, Kerala. He serves as an Assistant Professor in the Department of Philosophy at Govt. College for Women, Vazhutacaud, Trivandrum.

theologian, but as a philosopher as well, opens up new ways of thought about theorizing on body.¹ For attaining the objective of this essay, it explains first Aristotle's views on soul-body relation. It describes then Aquinas's ideas about soul-body relation. By examining the philosophy of Aquinas on body this study tries to further explain some of the underdeveloped aspects of his philosophy on body. For this purpose, it applies in this study a theological notion, resurrection. The intention of applying a theological notion in a philosophical study is to develop a genuinely novel approach to the notion of body that is perhaps possible in the light of the Aquinas's reading on Aristotle's study on soul-body relation. It opens up a new horizon of thought related to any attempt at theorizing body. It is also randomly indicated in this study that the application of the theological notion of resurrection in Aquinasian philosophy on soul-body relation surprisingly leads us to certain areas of resemblance that it shares with some present-day explanations on body such that body as a constructed entity articulated by the discourses and the transcendental excess this entity has within its historicized existence.²

Aristotle on Body-Soul Relation

It is well known that Aristotle had not elaborately dealt with the notion of body in his philosophical writings. But one may see that in his 'De Anima'³ the notion of soul as life principle is treated in close connection with the notion of body. Hence, we can say that Aristotle's interpretation on soul indirectly proposes a treatise on body also.

To Plato 'form' is an objective idealistic notion. In his theory of knowledge 'form' is placed at the top of the gradation of knowledge

¹ This aspect of the study is not highlighted in this essay. A comparative study can be initiated in its own right by analyzing various strands of contemporary philosophical views on body and their resemblance with that of Aquinasian views on soul-body relation.

² Aristotle, *De Anima, On the Soul*, (Tr. J.A. Smith, Introduction to Aristotle, 2nd Edition, Ed. Richard McKeon, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1973).

³ By presenting the 'Theory of Divided Line' Plato discusses in detail his theory of Form. This theory is detailed in almost all the Dialogues of Plato directly and indirectly. The theory of the Divided line is the Platonic theory of Knowledge. Plato speaks about four layers of Knowledge that function as the steps to obtain the Highest Good. The four layers of knowledge in the Platonic theory of knowledge are Eikhasis, Pistis, Dianoia, and Noesis. For a detailed discussion on the Theory of knowledge in Plato See Plato, *Republic, and Phaedo in Five Great Dialogues*, Tr. B. Jowett, D. Van Noster and Company Inc. (New York, 1942), 85-153; 221-495.

and being. He places 'matter' at the other end of the 'Divided Line'.⁴ Aristotle in his philosophical treatises critically revised the Platonic theory of 'form'. According to Aristotle, 'form' as individuating principle is inseparable from 'matter'. Form, which is potentially inherent in matter, is actualized as different possibilities of things. In Aristotle's view, the living- principle of matter, form, or soul actualizes the body of a thing. Here we can see that the Aristotelian treatise on soul turns out to be a treatise on body as well.

Aristotle begins his philosophical inquiry on the notion of soul by asking a question about the essence of it: what is soul? In his answer to the question about the essence of soul he calls it substance. To Aristotle substance is that which is neither predicable of a subject nor present in a subject. This means that a substance is something ultimate and independent of all other things, while the latter must depend upon the former. At the same time Aristotle argues that there must be some essential constituents in a substance, which is articulated in the activities of a thing. In the light of his views on substance, Aristotle tries to explain the essence of the soul. He states that the easiest way to obtain the most adequate explanation about soul as substance is to seek each of its forms appropriated as activities of a thing. In Book 2 of 'De Anima' he says that in order to know what soul is, we have to formulate the most general possible definition of the essential constituents of it. These essential constituents are appropriated in the activities of a thing. Aristotle says that generally philosophers are in the habit of recognizing the essential constituents of a substance as only one determinate kind of what it 'is', substance, and that is expressed in one of the following senses only in their explanations about them like, a) in the sense of matter or that which in itself is not 'a this'; b) in the sense of form or essence, which is that precisely in virtue of which a thing is called 'a this' and c) in the sense of that which is compounded of both a) and b).⁵ Aristotle favors the third position to explain the essential constituents of a substance. According to this position he describes matter as the principle of potentiality and form as the principle of actuality. Aristotle further states that in the composite of matter and form in the constitution of the substance, there are two modes of relation possible between them. They are related to one another as in the analogy of the relation of knowledge to the exercising of knowledge.

⁴ Plato, *Republic and Phaedo in Five Great Dialogues*, Tr. B. Jowett, D. Van Noster and Company Inc. (New York, 1942), 85-153; 221-495.

⁵ Aristotle, *De Anima, On the Soul*, 181.

After a thorough and critical study about the explanations given by his predecessors about the essential nature of soul, Aristotle defines it as *'that for the sake of which body is'*. Here the notion of *'that for the sake of which'* is interpreted in two senses by Aristotle: a) the end to achieve which and b) the being in whose interest anything is or is done. In these two senses Aristotle defines soul as the enmattering of the formulable essence.⁶ One thing we must note here is that in the Aristotelian definition of soul there is no multiplicity of forms like vegetative soul, animal soul and rational soul in human beings. To Aristotle 'form' is the single unity that constitutes the hylo-morphic constitution of body. In the light of Aristotle's philosophy of soul, the possession of form in the matter is to be understood in two senses: a) exercising of actuality in the body and b) the possession of actuality as principle in the body. Aristotle emphasizes the first sense in his philosophy. This means that body as the actuality of soul does not possess the soul merely as a principle of it, but rather actualizing it in its activities. To Aristotle, body is the lived-soul. It is in the light of this actualizing process of body we speak about soul as the living principle of the body; not the other way round.

According to Aristotle, the soul cannot be without a body, even while it cannot *be* a body. One can see that in order to consider the nature of soul-in-itself, i.e. soul *be* body, Aristotle has to move from metaphysics to Theology. In fact, Aristotle has made such a move from metaphysics to theology in his philosophy. If we consider soul *be* body then it is *Actus Purus*,⁷ God, which is *Thought-thinking-thought* in Aristotle's

⁶ Aristotle, *De Anima, On the Soul*, 182-187.

⁷ In the metaphysical order, according to Aristotle, the highest determinations of being are the 'Actuality' (entelechies) and the 'Potentiality' (dynamis). The former is the perfection, realization and the fullness of being. The latter is imperfection, incompleteness and perfectibility. Actuality is the determining principle and potentiality, the determinable one. The 'Actuality' and the 'potentiality' are categories. They are found in all beings, with an exception to the Supreme Cause, in whom there is no imperfection, and, therefore, no potentiality. He is the 'all- actuality', the 'Actus-Purus'. All other beings are composed of the actuality and the potentiality, a dualism, which is the general metaphysical formula for the dualism of the matter and the form, the body and the soul, the substance and the accident, the soul and its faculties and the passive and the active intellect. In the physical order, the potentiality and the actuality become the 'Matter' and the 'Form'. To these are to be added the Agent (Efficient Cause) and the End (Final Cause). But as the efficiency and the finality are to be reduced, in ultimate analysis, to the domain of the Form, we have in the physical order two ultimate principles of being, namely, the Matter and the Form.

philosophy. According to his metaphysical position, soul cannot be body. To *be* body, soul must always be in its lived-form. This means that soul is an actuality or formulable essence of something that possesses the potentiality of being besouled.

Against the argument of Aristotle on establishing the nature of the soul-body relation as hylo-morphic constitution, one can reasonably ask how the individuating principle of form is initiated in matter, which is potential for being besouled. Aristotle's answer to this question bears the traces of nostalgia about Platonic forms. Closely analyzing Aristotle's thinking on soul-body relation, Thomas Aquinas addresses in his philosophical thinking the afore-said issue of the initiation of the form into the matter.

Thomas Aquinas on Body-Soul Relation

Generally, Thomas Aquinas accepts Aristotle's doctrine of hylo-morphic composition of substance.⁸ He defines prime matter as pure potentiality and substantial form as the first act of a physical body. In Aquinas the first act means the principles that place the body in its specific class and the determination of its essence. According to Aquinas, matter cannot exist by itself, for to speak of a being actually existing without act or form is a contradiction. In the same way one should not think that matter precedes form temporally. Matter is always conjoined with the form. Form is the universal element that places an object in its class, in its species, making it to be, for example, a cat, a horse etc. It then needs to be individuated, in order that it should become the form of a particular substance. What is the principle of this individuation? Aquinas asserts that it can only be matter. But we have already noted that matter is of itself pure potentiality: it has not got those determinations that are necessary for individuating form. It is obvious that the accidental characteristics of quantity and so on of a thing are logically posterior to the hylo-morphic composition of the substance. Aquinas therefore introduces in his philosophical reflections on hylo-morphic composition

⁸ Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, Tr. Fathers of the English Dominican Province, Revised by Daniel J. Sullivan, (Vol.1. Question LXXXV. Treatise on Man), 378.

of substance a new notion as the principle of individuation: '*materia signata quantitate*'⁹ (matter assigned of quantity or individuation). This assigning of individuation is the capacity for exigency in matter, thanks to which it is being besouled and individuated. This exigency is expressed and realized as the actualization of the form in its conjoining with matter. This actualizing principle i.e. '*materia signata quantitate*' cannot be treated separately from the actualizing body i.e. the lived body.

After the elaboration on the individuating principle in the hylomorphic constitution of substance, Aquinas extends his discussion to the question of the dissociation of soul and body. He explains it in the light of the transcendental characteristic of form. We have already seen in the previous section that by treating the question of the nature of soul-in-itself, Aristotle turned from metaphysics to the sphere of Theology. But Aquinas, by analyzing the living principle in human beings i.e. intellect, highlights in his philosophy, without turning to the field of theology, the possibility of the existence of soul without having its spatio-temporal actualization in the body. How is such a possibility of the existence of soul possible? In order to answer this question, we have to closely look into the philosophy of Aquinas on human soul and its characteristic of intellect.

Aquinas elaborately discusses in his philosophy the various modes of the actualizations of soul in body.¹⁰ He argues that certain modes of actualizations of soul in body need not strictly adhere to the spatio-temporal structure of body as such. These modes of actualizations of soul in body transcend the spatio-temporal confinements of bodily existence due to the characteristic of exigency in matter. But Aquinas is careful to specifically state that despite this transcendence of a mode of actualization, it is not wholly separated from the individuating principle of the body i.e. the principle of the '*materia signata quantitate*' of the matter. According to Aquinas, the exigency in matter functions as the body for the transcendence of form. The transcendence of form needs

⁹ For a detailed discussion on Thomas Aquinas's idea of Psychology and on the notion of '*Materia signata quantitates*' See Frederick Copelston S.J. *History of Philosophy*, Vol.2 *Augustine to Scotus* Ch.37. part vii *St. Thomas Aquinas: Psychology*, (Image Book, New York, 1985), 375-387.

¹⁰ Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, 385-395.

a body to execute its actualizations, in spite of its separation from the concerned spatio-temporal bodily existence.

Aquinas asserts that the soul is indeed the form of the body. It always retains its aptitude to inform a body, precisely because it is naturally the form of the body; but it is nonetheless, a rational soul and its powers are not exhausted in informing the body alone. The transcendental status of form is both in relation and in non-relation to the exigency of matter. What would be the nature of such an enmattering of the formulable essence i.e. the conjoining of the transcendence of form with the exigency of matter? In this study, I call it the resurrected body.

St. Thomas argues that the rational soul must be spiritual and a subsistent form because it is capable of knowing the nature of all bodies. At the same time, he insists that the rational soul is natural as well, for the soul is united to the body in its nature and that their union is for the good of the soul. This means that Aquinas does not see the spiritual as a dissociation from the material. The idea of *Thought-thinking-thought* in Aristotle favors such a dissociation of matter from the form. Aquinas does not hesitate to say that the state of separation is *praeter naturam* and the soul's mode of cognition in the state of separation is also *praeter naturam*. Thus, Aquinas does not lead his thought on body-soul relation to the theological sphere as Aristotle does. But how can this contradictory view on body-soul relation as relation and non-relation be reconciled in the light of Aquinas's philosophical explanations? I apply the theological notion of resurrection to explain the reconciliation between these two apparently contradictory views in the philosophy of Aquinas.

What Happens to Body in Resurrection?

It is in the New Testament Gospels that we see explanations about Jesus, the resurrected one in detail. According to the canonical Gospel narratives, He appears to his disciples as resurrected after his crucifixion and death. The explanations given by both Synoptic and Johannine Gospels present the appearance of Jesus as both historical and meta-historical.¹¹ According to the Gospels, the resurrected Jesus shows his nailed hands and pierced side to his disciples. Though the doors are shut, he enters the room without opening them and reveals

¹¹ See *The New Testament RSV* Jn. 20: 19-20; Jn. 20: 26-30; Lk. Ch.24; Mt. Ch.28

himself to his disciples who are hiding there for fear of death. The resurrected one is presented by the evangelists as one who is continuing his earthly existence, but at the same time transcending the limitations of his spatio-temporal existence. According to the account given by the Gospels of the New Testament, the resurrected Jesus is both related and not-related to his earthly life. According to the descriptions of St. Paul, the resurrection is the function of the spirit. The body is renewed by the spirit. In his letter to the Church of the Corinthians, he presents the concept of a spiritual body in relation to the notion of resurrection.¹²

Hylo-morphic Union of Substance as Resurrection

We can see that in Aquinas's explanations about substance, the exigency of matter relates the transcendence of form to the body and the transcendence of form unties this relation from the existing situation of the body. According to Aquinas, this tying and untying between transcendence of form and exigency of matter do not occur separately in time; rather they occur simultaneously without one having precedence over the other.

Hylo-morphic constitution, according to Aquinas is explainable only if we accept the transcendence of form and the exigency of matter. In the light of Aquinas's philosophy, the spatio-temporal constitution of body, whether it is understood as essential in nature or explained as discursively formed, cannot ignore the fact of its transcendence. Body and soul are not separate realities in the Thomistic view. Rather they are united in nature. At the same time this union cannot be treated by confining it in its historicized existence. By resurrected body I mean that body which is the result of the hylo-morphic constitution and is simultaneously tied to historicized existence and untied from it. Body is always a resurrected body and cannot but be one.

Conclusion

In his philosophy on body-soul relation, Aquinas problematizes the dualistic approach to it. This article is an attempt at applying the theological notion of resurrection in the philosophy of Aquinas on body-soul relations in order to present the nuances of certain underdeveloped aspects of this ever-recurring theme in the history of philosophy. The

¹² See *The New Testament RSV*. St. Paul's First Letter to The Church of Corinth. 1Cor. 15: 20-46; Specially see 1Cor. 15: 44

notion of the resurrected body does not imply the negation of the lived-existence. It problematizes all the dualistic approaches that tend to separate the principles, which compose the reality of substance to their extremes. In contemporary philosophy, we see many attempts that challenge the dualistic approaches on reality. Ever-recurring themes of philosophy such those about subject-object dualism, gender distinctions, questions on the self and the other, synchronic and the diachronic temporality and the engagement of philosophers with these themes indicate the directions in which contemporary thinking is moving. Regardless of their complex details and minute differences, they show that they all hold up the notion of transcendence as irreducible to any kind of dualistic principles in their extremes. Whether this notion is closely related or not to the theme of the body-soul relation in a medieval thinker's philosophy is yet to be closely probed and discussed. Yet this article claims that it has tried to examine the notion of body-soul relation in Aquinas in a newer perspective that has something to say about the problematization of dualism in medieval thinking.

Bibliography

- Aristotle, *De Anima, On the Soul*, Tr. J.A. Smith, Introduction to Aristotle, 2nd Edition, Ed. Richard Mckeon, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1973.
- Aquinas.Thomas *Summa Theologica*, Tr. Fathers of the English Dominican Province, Revised by Daniel J. Sullivan, Vol.1. Question LXXV. Treatise on Man. London, Burns, Oates, and Washbourne 1911 and Westminster Christian Classics, Md., 1981.
- Copelston, Frederick S.J. *History of Philosophy*, Vol.2 *Augustine to Scotus* Ch.37. part vii *St. Thomas Aquinas: Psychology*, New York, Image Book, 1985.
- Dillet, Benoit, Ian Mckanzie, Porter, Ed. *The Edinburgh Companion to Post Structuralism*, London. Edinburgh Press, 2013.
- Plato, Tr.B. Jowett, *Five Great Dialogues*, New York, D. Van Noster and Company Inc. 1942.
- The New Testament*, Revised Standard Version., the Division of Christian Education of the National Council of the Churches of Christ, USA,1952.

IMPERIAL TACTICS AND RESILIENCE: A CHILDIST PERSPECTIVE ON MEPHIBOSHETH'S JOURNEY

- Sam T Rajkumar*

Introduction

Prophetic consciousness is the awakened perception that transcends the present moment, foreseeing the future's potential and guiding humanity toward collective evolution. It involves a connection to intuition, spirituality and divine guidance, allowing individuals to offer wisdom, guidance, or warnings to others based on their insights. It emphasizes prophetic ideas, like the relation of God to the world, the concepts of providence and history, justice and mercy, etc. According to theologian Walter Brueggemann, "The task of prophetic ministry is to nurture, nourish, and evoke a consciousness and perception alternative to the consciousness and perception of the dominant culture around us."¹ Prophetic consciousness is not solely concerned with denouncing the present order, but also with kindling hope and inspiration towards a future redefined by compassion and restoration. Amidst conflict, it fosters a deep-seated anticipation of the renewal promised by divine providence.

In the realm of religious praxis, this consciousness manifests as a beacon of dissent, challenging institutional complacency and the allure of power. It embodies a steadfast commitment to the welfare of all, particularly the most vulnerable, such as children caught in the midst of conflict zones like Manipur, Ukraine and Gaza. It also underscores an unwavering solidarity with marginalized communities and a sacred duty to steward the Earth's precious resources. Through the lens of prophetic consciousness and childist methodology, the Mephibosheth narrative in 2 Samuel 9 is explored here. This examination not only sheds light on

* Rev. Sam T Rajkumar is an accomplished minister with a strong background in children's ministry. He is currently pursuing a Master's degree in Biblical Studies (Old Testament) at United Theological College, Bangalore.

¹ Walter Brueggemann, *The Prophetic Imagination*, 40th Anniversary Edition (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2018), 3.

the profound impacts of war but also prompts reflections and practical interventions to empower and protect children in conflict zones.

Childist Methodology

The concept of childism has been present in academia for decades, though it remains unfamiliar to many. Ethicist John Wall defines childism as “the effort to respond to the experiences of children by transforming understanding and practices for all.”² Building on Wall’s framework, the term childist is used to describe interpretations that prioritize the agency and actions of children and youth in biblical texts, rather than portraying them primarily as passive, victimized, or marginalized. Similar to feminist and womanist approaches, childist interpretation explores the construction and function of various biblical characters while challenging traditional hegemonic assumptions.³ The initial step in childist interpretation involves reading the text to identify and acknowledge the presence of child characters. To delve into these characters more deeply, narrative critical method is employed, placing the child at the forefront of analysis. This approach has a systematic six-step process⁴ aimed at providing a comprehensive understanding of children who are overlooked in the biblical text.

Julie Parker applied this methodology in her book and termed the intersection of biblical studies and childhood studies as “childist” methodology. She defined it as, “to identify and appreciate the influence and importance of promising, compelling young biblical characters.”⁵

² John Wall, *Ethics in Light of Childhood* (Washington: Georgetown University Press, 2010), 3.

³ Kathleen Gallagher Elkins and Julie Faith Parker, “Children in Biblical Narrative and Childist Interpretation,” in *The Oxford Handbook of Biblical Narrative*, edited by Danna Nolan Fewell (New York: Oxford University Press, 2016), 589.

⁴ Firstly, the interpreter concentrates on the setting, characters, and plot within a given passage. This involves carefully examining the context in which the child characters exist, as well as their relationships with other characters. Next, the interpreter extracts relevant information related to the child or children and proceeds to offer interpretations based on narrative details, cultural or historical insights, and connections with other biblical texts involving children.

⁵ Julie Faith Parker, *Value and Vulnerable: Children in the Hebrew Bible, especially the Elisha Cycle* (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2017), 17.

As Bunge asserts, “it examines the biblical texts through the lens or category of the child.”⁶ In this paper, Mephibosheth is placed at the forefront of the analysis, challenging traditional interpretations of biblical texts and prioritizing his experiences and agency within the narrative of 2 Samuel 9. Through narrative critical method, Mephibosheth’s journey from vulnerability to resilience is explored within the context of war, shedding light on his unique contributions and challenges. This approach cultivates empathy and solidarity by advocating for proactive interventions informed by prophetic ideals of compassion and justice, aiming to address the distinct needs and vulnerabilities of children affected by war and conflict.

Analysis Through Childist Lens

i. Historical Context

The narrative of Mephibosheth unfolds within the broader context of the Court History or Succession Narrative.⁷ The death of Saul and his son Jonathan in the armed conflict with the Philistines brought chaos to the royal house on multiple levels.⁸ Following Saul’s demise, the focus shifts from Saul’s royal house to David, who had a prime opportunity to establish himself as king. After advancing David’s character, the narrative returns to Saul’s royal house to inform the reader about the succession, highlighting the ongoing armed conflict between the houses of Saul and David.⁹

ii. Mephibosheth’s Background

The central child character, Mephibosheth, is the son of Jonathan and grandson of Saul. He becomes crippled when he is five years old,¹⁰

⁶ Marcia J. Bunge, *The Child in the Bible* (Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2008), xviii.

⁷ Harold O. Forshey, “Court narrative,” in *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, vol. 1, edited by David Noel Freedman (New York: Doubleday, 1992), 1172-1179.

⁸ First, chaos would have erupted within the royal house regarding who would take over the reign. Second, the houses of Saul and David continued to engage in violent confrontations.

⁹ In 2 Samuel 3:1, the reader is informed that “the war between the house of Saul and the house of David lasted a long time. David grew stronger and stronger, while the house of Saul grew weaker and weaker.”

¹⁰ cf. 2 Samuel 4:4

due to the violence surrounding their deaths.¹¹ Machir¹² plays a crucial role in sheltering Mephibosheth from the political turmoil and potential threats to his life. His actions reflect a father's protective instinct and the sacrifices made to ensure the safety and well-being of the child. Ziba, a servant of the royal household, discloses Meribaal's whereabouts in Lo-debar, leading to his restoration of property and a place at David's table.¹³ David, the King fulfils his promise to Jonathan by demonstrating commitment to his covenant and also loyalty within the royal court.¹⁴

iii. David's Actions

However, it's essential to recognize the broader context of David's reign, characterized by military conquests and expansionist policies. David's preoccupation with territorial expansion contributed to the vulnerability of countless children, including Mephibosheth, who became a victim of the consequences of war. David's military endeavours, while fulfilling his political ambitions, also perpetuated a cycle of violence and instability that disproportionately affected the most marginalized individuals.¹⁵ Therefore, while David's actions towards Mephibosheth may appear benevolent on the surface, they also highlight the broader systemic issues of violence and vulnerability inherent in societies driven by war.

iv. Psychological Impact on Mephibosheth

When summoned to David's court, Mephibosheth's reaction is one of fear and humility. His self-identification as a "dead dog"¹⁶ highlights

¹¹ Diana Vikander Edelman, "Mephibosheth" in *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, vol. 4, edited by David Noel Freedman (New York: Doubleday, 1992), 696-697.

¹² Machir, the son of Ammiel, played a significant role in biblical narrative. According to 2 Samuel 9:4-5, Machir sheltered Mephibosheth, in his home at Lo-debar, demonstrating loyalty to Saul's lineage and ultimately gaining favour with David. See Patrick Graham, "Machir" in *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, vol. 4..., 458-460.

¹³ Diana Vikander Edelman, "Merib-Baal" in *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, vol. 4..., 701-702.

¹⁴ Walter Brueggemann, *First and Second Samuel. Interpretation. A Bible Commentary for Teaching and Preaching* (Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster John Knox Press, 2012), 291-293.

¹⁵ cf. 2 Samuel 8: 1-14.

¹⁶ cf. 2 Samuel 9:8

his perceived worthlessness and vulnerability. This dehumanizing self-assessment underscores the profound impact of the war and the ensuing political changes on his psyche and status.¹⁷ Despite his noble lineage, Mephibosheth views himself as insignificant and powerless, a tragic reflection of how war can strip individuals of their dignity and sense of worth.

Mephibosheth's disability should not be seen merely as the result of an accident where his nurse dropped him, resulting in a crippling injury. The context within which Mephibosheth, an able child at the time, became disabled matters. It was during armed conflict that Mephibosheth became paralyzed. David's actions toward Mephibosheth, while presented as acts of kindness and a way to fulfil his oath to Jonathan,¹⁸ also have troubling aspects. When Mephibosheth is invited into the royal house, the psychological damage is already done.¹⁹ With his disabilities, it would be impossible for him to marshal an army to rival David.²⁰ Furthermore, Mephibosheth being brought so close to the king meant living on a knife's edge.

v. Imperial Tactics and Control

David's kindness towards Mephibosheth exhibits an imperial tactic of war: disabling more than just physically so that the disabled person becomes reliant on and consumes the imperial goods. David's actions were intended to keep Mephibosheth under constant check, reliant, and, where possible, set him up for failure to render him killable.²¹ Indeed, Mephibosheth vanishes from the story later after the betrayal by his servant Ziba, who informed David that Mephibosheth was hoping for the kingdom to be restored to Saul's house. This accusation implied that

¹⁷ Jeremy Schipper, "Why do you still speak of your affairs?": Polyphony in Mephibosheth's exchanges with David in 2 Samuel," *Vetus Testamentum* 54/3 (July, 2004): 347-348.

¹⁸ 2 Samuel 9; 16:1-4; 21:7

¹⁹ cf. 2 Samuel 9:6-8

²⁰ William R. Farmer, ed., *The International Bible Commentary. An Ecumenical Commentary for The Twenty-First Century* (Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 2019), 649-650.

²¹ cf. 2 Samuel 16:1-4 and 19:24-30.

Mephibosheth wanted to seize the opportunity of dysfunction within David's royal house to be declared king over Israel. As a result, the parcels of land restored to Mephibosheth were transferred to Ziba (2 Sam 16:4), effectively reversing the kindness shown to him. David's later actions toward Mephibosheth render his earlier benevolent actions questionable, as the disabled Mephibosheth becomes a victim yet again.²²

The empire had the right to maim, take property, and kill as a tactic to manage the population. David used imperialist tactics to kill and maim but also presented himself as kind while looking for solutions for Mephibosheth, who was crippled.²³ While his hand was involved in the actions that rendered Mephibosheth disabled, the benevolence towards Mephibosheth was intended to keep David in power while debilitating Saul's household. The empire inflicts injury while at the same time showing kindness to keep the conquered under submission.²⁴ The empire has power over life and death; therefore, it can injure and let live. The Mephibosheth story is thus based on the imperial ideology of injury and benevolence.

vi. Mephibosheth's Resilience

In the ancient context of war, children lost their parents and their abilities, and those who escaped with their lives in case of defeat were not just displaced but were turned into enslaved people, with the girl children having to suffer from sexual violations and rape and forced marriages.²⁵ Mephibosheth's disability and the death of his family, resulted from the tumultuous times of war and political upheaval.²⁶ The experience of displacement and isolation from his family's heritage would have undoubtedly shaped his identity and sense of belonging.

²² Christopher Rouse, "Scripture and the Disabled: Redeeming Mephibosheth's Identity," *Journal of Pentecostal Theology* 17/2, 191.

²³ 2 Samuel 5:6-9; 8:1-14; 12:31.

²⁴ Hulisani Ramantswana, "Disability as a Symbol of Terror: Rereading the David Narrative in Light of Armed Conflicts in Africa," *Biblical Theology Bulletin* 53/4 (2023): 244-245.

²⁵ cf. Numbers 31:17-18; Judges 21:11-12.

²⁶ Stephen J. Andrews and Robert D. Bergen, *Holman Old Testament Commentary I & II Samuel* (Nashville, Tennessee: Broadman & Holman Publishers, 2009), 317-319.

Mephibosheth's actions reveal his capacity to navigate his circumstances with agency and resilience. Despite his physical disability and the political vulnerability of being Saul's descendant, he demonstrates initiative by responding to David's summons and presenting himself with humility yet dignity. While David's offer of kindness could be interpreted as an attempt to control or pacify a potential rival, Mephibosheth's acceptance of the restoration of his family's lands and a place at David's table can also be seen as reclaiming his rightful heritage and status. In doing so, Mephibosheth challenges the derogatory meaning of his name, "mouth of shame," proving through his actions that he possesses strength and self-worth despite the challenges he faces. Thus, the narrative illustrates not only David's political manoeuvring but also Mephibosheth's resilience and assertion of his rightful place.

vii. Parallels with Other Biblical Figures

The biblical accounts of Joseph, Ishmael, Esther, and Jesus parallels aspects of Mephibosheth's story.²⁷ Just as Mephibosheth faces displacement and vulnerability due to his family's history, these characters navigate challenging circumstances from a young age. Whether sold into slavery like Joseph, or cast into the wilderness like Ishmael, each character demonstrates resilience and faith in the face of hardship. Similarly, figures like Esther and Jesus exemplify courage and determination in confronting life-threatening situations, ultimately fulfilling their divine purposes despite their humble beginnings. Through these parallel narratives, the biblical text underscores the enduring strength and purpose that can emerge from adversity, resonating with Mephibosheth's own journey of survival and redemption.

War's Impact on Children

In examining the ramifications of war through a lens of prophetic consciousness, research underscores the heightened vulnerability of children, leading to enduring psychological scars such as PTSD, anxiety, and depression.²⁸ These adversities disrupt their cognitive-

²⁷ cf. Genesis 37:3-4, Genesis 21:9-21, Jeremiah 1:4-10, Esther 2:5-18, and Luke 2:41-52.

²⁸ Bernardo Carpiniello, "The mental health costs of armed conflicts-a review of systematic reviews conducted on refugees, asylum-seekers and people living in war zones," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 2840/20 (February, 2023): 13.

emotional processing, often manifesting in behaviours like aggression or withdrawal.²⁹ The consequences extend beyond physical harm, as children born of wartime rape face stigma and socio-economic marginalization. Loss of caregivers and disruptions to social and emotional development exacerbate mental health issues, leading to high rates of depression and anxiety among war-affected children.³⁰

Prophetic consciousness acknowledges the complex interplay of individual characteristics and environmental influences in shaping a child's response to trauma,³¹ emphasizing the need for culturally competent, trauma-informed psychological services to foster resilience and recovery. The cognitive impacts of war-related stress and displacement emphasize the imperative to protect vulnerable children. War experiences disrupt cognitive functioning, leading to developmental delays and impairments in memory and attention. Research on Syrian refugee children reveal how war-related experiences and suboptimal conditions contribute to poor mental health and developmental delays, affecting various cognitive domains.³² Mitigating the allostatic load³³ on children aligns with the prophetic vision of fostering holistic well-being and justice. By prioritizing the psychological, social, and cognitive well-being of affected children, prophetic ideals can be embodied on a global scale.

Theological Reflections on Child Suffering and Prophetic Response

The question of theodicy and the problem of evil, particularly concerning child suffering, is intricate and emotionally charged. 2

²⁹ Iman Farajallah, et al., "The Psychosocial Impacts of War and Armed Conflict on Children," *Psychiatric Times*, accessed 15 April 2024, <https://www.psychiatrictimes.com/view/the-psychosocial-impacts-of-war-and-armed-conflict-on-children>.

³⁰ Joanna Santa Barbara, "Impact of War on Children and Imperative to End War," *Croatian Medical Journal* 47/6 (December, 2006): 892.

³¹ Michelle Liu, "War and Children," *The American Journal of Psychiatry Residents' Journal* 12/7 (July, 2017): 3.

³² For more details on the research conducted, see Livia Hazer & Gustaf Gredebäck, "The effects of war, displacement, and trauma on child development," *Palgrave Communications* 10/1 (December, 2023): 1-19.

³³ The accumulation of stressors over time, known as allostatic load, can further hinder child development, leading to long-lasting maladaptive outcomes that persist into adulthood.

Samuel 9 doesn't explicitly address theodicy but highlights themes of compassion, restoration, and divine favour. While no definitive answers exist, various perspectives³⁴ shed light on the nature of suffering and evil and offer ways to respond with compassion and understanding. Prophetic calls for justice and compassion towards children have deep roots in religious teachings, spanning from the Old Testament prophets like Amos and Hosea to the New Testament teachings of Jesus.³⁵ These teachings emphasize the intrinsic value of children and the imperative to prioritize their well-being in society. Certain religious institutions have embraced this ethos, advocating for a preferential option for children.³⁶ Moreover, secular organizations and movements also recognize children's vulnerability and advocate for their protection and support within society.

Despite embodying remarkable resilience, children remain inherently vulnerable due to societal structures and norms that prioritize adult needs and perspectives. While children demonstrate resilience, their ability to thrive is hindered by environments primarily designed for adults, which lack adequate consideration for children's unique needs and rights. Children need adults as protectors, yet these are often the same adults who wage war and exploit them. Therefore, adults must transform from war-wagers to protectors of children, recognizing that protecting children is protecting God's people. Moreover, children are full humans with a dignified place in society, possessing wisdom that must be explored and valued by adults.

³⁴ One perspective highlights the belief that God's goodness can ultimately bring about good from evil, such as raising awareness for peace and justice through the suffering of children in war zones. Another emphasizes the importance of lament and justice in acknowledging and mourning child suffering rather than seeking simplistic explanations. Lastly, it proposes that suffering and evil serve a purpose in a greater divine plan, suggesting that they will ultimately lead to a greater good. See J. Reid Perkins-Buzo, "Theodicy in the Face of Children's Suffering and Death," *The Journal of Pastoral Care* 48/2 (Summer, 1994); Nick Trakakis, "Theodicy: The Solution to the Problem of Evil, or Part of the Problem?" *Sophia* 47/2 (July, 2008); N. N. Trakakis, "Anti-theodicy," in *The Problem of Evil: Eight Views in Dialogue*, edited by N. N. Trakakis (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018).

³⁵ cf. Amos 5:24, Hosea 14:4; Matthew 18:5; 25:40.

³⁶ Alfred Kah Meng Pang, "Renewing a Prophetic Mysticism for Teaching Children Justly: A Lasallian Provocation," *Religions* 13/10 (September, 2022): 6-7.

In times of escalating violence, immediate solidarity with war victims is essential. Recognizing deaths, dignity violations, and the vulnerability of the underprivileged is crucial. Every moment is an opportunity for radical change. Historically, Old Testament messiahs emerged to liberate people by understanding the times and resisting violence on behalf of the vulnerable. Today, killings, inadequate education, and lack of prophetic vision plague us, silencing intergenerational conversations through the killing and disappearance of children.³⁷ These acts violate the divine covenant, which values children as vital participants in the community, thus undermining this sacred bond between communities.

Practical Applications

Child-centered approaches to conflict resolution prioritize the development of children's social and emotional skills, empowering them to navigate disputes and foster positive relationships. Strategies include individual negotiation,³⁸ conflict resolution education,³⁹ peer mediation programs,⁴⁰ and fostering peace-making skills.⁴¹ These approaches emphasize empowering children as active agents in peacebuilding efforts.⁴² The church plays a crucial role in safeguarding children in conflict zones by influencing social norms, providing humanitarian aid, nurturing spirituality, and advocating for children's rights.⁴³ They serve

³⁷ Rohan Gideon, "Violence, Vulnerability and Kairos in Palestine-Israel Conflicts: Biblical Reflections. Deuteronomy 6: 10-25," *NCC Review* CXLIV/1 (January-February 2024): 28.

³⁸ Individual negotiation empowers children to resolve conflicts by identifying issues, negotiating solutions, and implementing agreed-upon resolutions.

³⁹ Conflict resolution and peace education curriculum instill values of peace, social justice, and problem-solving, creating participatory and caring environments.

⁴⁰ Peer mediation programs allow children to independently resolve disputes, drawing from skills learned through individual negotiation.

⁴¹ Fostering peace-making skills in the classroom involves acknowledging and modelling peaceful behaviors, respecting children's contributions, and celebrating positive stories of peace.

⁴² For a detailed reading on Child-centered conflict resolution strategies, see Harriet Field, *A Wholistic Approach to Conflict Resolution*, Association for Childhood Education International Conference (Minneapolis: ERIC, 1996), 4-7.

⁴³ Malia Robinson, "Conflict, Child Protection and Religious Communities: A Review and Recommendations on Enhancing Protection through Partnership," *JLIFLC*, accessed 29 April 2024, <https://jliflc.com/resources/conflict-child-protection-religious-communities>.

as mediators between stakeholders, promote interfaith dialogue, and build peaceful societies. Ethical considerations in research involving children include safeguarding their rights as research subjects, ensuring informed consent, and balancing participation with protection. Researchers must prioritize children's well-being and navigate ethical principles with care.

Conclusion

The Mephibosheth narrative serves as a poignant reminder of the enduring impact of violence on the most vulnerable members of society. It invites the envisioning of a future where every child is afforded the safety, security, and opportunity they deserve. By embracing compassion, justice, and solidarity, a world can be built where children thrive and flourish, free from the scars of war. Reflecting on the transformative power of empathy and action, it is crucial to also recognize the need to challenge imperialist ideologies, such as those embodied by David, who inflicts injury while simultaneously showing kindness to maintain dominance over the conquered. Rejecting such contradictions is essential, fostering a world where genuine peace and justice prevail, free from the manipulative use of benevolence as a tool of control. Protecting and empowering the most vulnerable among us, ensuring that their voices are heard and their rights are upheld, honours the prophetic tradition of advocating for a future defined by peace, justice, and the inherent dignity of every child.

Bibliography

- Andrews, Stephen J. and Robert D. Bergen. *Holman Old Testament Commentary I & II Samuel*. Nashville, Tennessee: Broadman & Holman Publishers, 2009.
- Barbara, Joanna Santa. "Impact of War on Children and Imperative to End War." *Croatian Medical Journal* 47/6 (December, 2006): 891-894.
- Brueggemann, Walter. *First and Second Samuel. Interpretation. A Bible Commentary for Teaching and Preaching*. Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster John Knox Press, 2012.

Brueggemann, Walter. *The Prophetic Imagination*. 40th Anniversary Edition. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2018.

Bunge, Marcia J. *The Child in the Bible*. Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2008.

Carpiniello, Bernardo. "The mental health costs of armed conflicts-a review of systematic reviews conducted on refugees, asylum-seekers and people living in war zones." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 2840/20 (February, 2023): 1-16.

Edelman, Diana Vikander. "Mephibosheth." In *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Vol. 4. Edited by David Noel Freedman. New York: Doubleday, 1992.

Elkins, Kathleen Gallagher and Julie Faith Parker. "Children in Biblical Narrative and Childist Interpretation." In *The Oxford Handbook of Biblical Narrative*. Edited by Danna Nolan Fewell. New York: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Farajallah, Iman. et al., "The Psychosocial Impacts of War and Armed Conflict on Children." *Psychiatric Times*. Accessed 15 April 2024. <https://www.psychiatristimes.com/view/the-psychosocial-impacts-of-war-and-armed-conflict-on-children>.

Farmer, William R. ed., *The International Bible Commentary. An Ecumenical Commentary for The Twenty-First Century*. Bangalore: Theological Publications in India, 2019.

Field, Harriet. *A Wholistic Approach to Conflict Resolution*. Association for Childhood Education International Conference. Minneapolis: ERIC, 1996.

Forshey, Harold O. "Court narrative." In *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Vol. 1. Edited by David Noel Freedman. New York: Doubleday, 1992.

Gideon, Rohan. "Violence, Vulnerability and Kairos in Palestine-Israel Conflicts: Biblical Reflections. Deuteronomy 6: 10-25." *NCC Review* CXLIV/1 (January- February 2024): 28.

Graham, Patrick. "Machir." In *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Vol. 4. Edited by David Noel Freedman. New York: Doubleday, 1992.

- Hazer, Livia. And Gustaf Gredebäck. "The effects of war, displacement, and trauma on child development." *Palgrave Communications* 10/1 (December, 2023): 1-19.
- Liu, Michelle "War and Children." *The American Journal of Psychiatry Residents' Journal* 12/7 (July, 2017): 3-5.
- Pang, Alfred Kah Meng. "Renewing a Prophetic Mysticism for Teaching Children Justly: A Lasallian Provocation." *Religions* 13/10 (September, 2022): 1-14.
- Parker, Julie Faith. *Value and Vulnerable: Children in the Hebrew Bible, especially the Elisha Cycle*. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2017.
- Perkins-Buzo, J. Reid. "Theodicy in the Face of Children's Suffering and Death." *The Journal of Pastoral Care* 48/2 (Summer, 1994): 155-161.
- Ramantswana, Hulisani. "Disability as a Symbol of Terror: Rereading the David Narrative in Light of Armed Conflicts in Africa." *Biblical Theology Bulletin* 53/4 (2023): 238-249.
- Robinson, Malia. "Conflict, Child Protection and Religious Communities" JLIFLC. Accessed 29 April 2024. <https://jliflc.com/resources/conflict-child-protection-religious-communities>.
- Rotenstreich, Nathan. "On Prophetic Consciousness." *The Journal of Religion* 54/3 (July, 1974): 185-198.
- Rouse, Christopher. "Scripture and the Disabled: Redeeming Mephibosheth's Identity." *Journal of Pentecostal Theology* 17/2 (2008): 183-199.
- Schipper, Jeremy. "Why do you still speak of your affairs?": Polyphony in Mephibosheth's exchanges with David in 2 Samuel." *Vetus Testamentum* 54/3 (July, 2004): 344-351.
- Trakakis, N. N. "Anti-theodicy." In *The Problem of Evil: Eight Views in Dialogue*. Edited by N. N. Trakakis. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018.
- Trakakis, Nick. "Theodicy: The Solution to the Problem of Evil, or Part of the Problem?" *Sophia* 47/2 (July, 2008): 161-191.
- Wall, John. *Ethics in Light of Childhood*. Washington: Georgetown University Press, 2010.

C.O.P.E.C. AND INDIA

**Excerpt from Rev. William Paton's Paper Presented
before Calcutta Missionary Conference
(Vol. XLIV, June 1924, Pg. 203-214)**

“The devising of godly phrases is a perilously easy business,” says the leader-writer of one of the great London dailies in an article on the Conference on Christian Politics, Economics and Citizenship (C.O.P.E.C.), which was held at Birmingham from April 7th to 13th, and which has become familiar to a multitude of people under the initials which make up the convenient, if mysterious word, “Copec.” If this Conference, so long and eagerly expected, were to be nothing more than a gigantic factory for a godly phrase, it would be worth much less than the paper on which its very lengthy reports are written. But it is because Copec represents the most serious attempt ever made by the Christian Church in any land to get to grips with the Christian doctrine for society, that it claims our attention, and makes it imperative on all Christians to understand what this enterprise really involves, both in the realm of thought and that of action. From the time, almost four years ago, when the first plans for this Conference were being laid (I may say here that the example of the great World Missionary Conference held at Edinburgh in 1910 has been continuously in the minds of its promoters) there has been an almost incredible amount of sheer hard work put into the preparation. I do not mean merely in regard to the organization of the Conference as such, for that is a comparatively minor matter, but in securing that on each of the subjects discussed there should be an extensive preliminary study by people well qualified to undertake it. If the Conference had not been held, the movement leading up to it would have been abundantly worthwhile. I understand that no less than 150,000 copies of the different study outlines were circulated, and the reports of the commissions, when finally drafted, represent not merely the views of the people, some of them eminent, who sign the reports, but the discussions, thought and prayer of a great multitude of Chris

tians besides. It is, therefore, I think, not too much to claim that Copeck is something of a landmark in the history of Christianity and that the work associated with the name deserves both our gratitude and our careful consideration.

There is a very careful discussion of the relation of the Church to politics, The Church is not the organ of the State, neither the State the organ of the Church each has its own function and method and outlook: The Church will almost always have to advocate a higher morality than the State, and any share she can have in the action of political parties can never exhaust her duty or be truly characteristic of her. If the Church approaches the political arena it should be with much caution and with the determination to minimize the merely coercive elements in the work of the State. Moreover, says the report:

The Church must also beware of so relying on the State to regulate moral evils through the influence of the prison and the police court as to neglect its own distinctive responsibility for renewing the mind and will of the nation by moral and spiritual influences: there is surely some ground for the accusation that the Church's resort to legislation against the evils of intemperance and gambling is the measure of its own lack of moral influence and spiritual power in the nation at large.

But the report is firm against the idea that Christianity has nothing to do with social activity; and equally, against the idea that politics are a kind of chemistry or mathematics with which moral and spiritual considerations have no concern. It urges that the main duty of the Church is to supply the motive power which will enable issues to be judged in a Christian light; that the political, arena should never be entered unless the issues are clearly moral; that more help should be given to clergy and laity to form instructed Christian judgments on current national issues that the Church should be alert to seize chances for reconciling work, that Christians should strive to carry more of the Christian spirit into political and municipal life, and that not least the Church can help by exhibiting within herself the spectacle of a Christian fellowship.

Much is also said of the need for the education of the members of the Church, clergy and laity, children and adults, in the elements of social duty and principle, and a number of very sound practical hints are given

as to how this may be done. The matter of Church discipline is touched on; while it is held that such discipline must always be redemptive and not merely retributory, it is also pointed out that the present practice of most Church bodies is to limit Church censure to the sins of self-indulgence. Much useful help is given in suggesting topics of burning national importance on which Christian direction might be given far more explicitly than is how currently the case, some, it is suggested, the Church can do no more than commend for study in the light of Christian principle, eg., the best way to remove unemployment; while on others she can speak with authority, e.g., on the application of Christian principles to the selection of investments, or in condemnation of sharp practice in trade, or of restriction of output for personal advantage.

The report of the "Commission on Politics" covers a great deal of ground. It contains a strong defence of the religious value of the State and the nature of the allegiance it may claim, with a strong repudiation of the idea that as a "secular and worldly thing it has no claim of Christian obedience. Conscientious resistance to the State there may indeed be, but it must be in the name of God, and Christians must not take that name in vain." But for the Christian, the Church must overshadow the State. Men must fix their hopes not on Caesar but on Christ. "Whatever contributions politics may be able to bring to the accomplishment of God's purpose, the redemption of man's nature must depend upon means utterly beyond the scope of human policy." The problems of representative government are discussed it is worth noting that representative government is not treated as an easy thing but a very difficult thing to maintain the relation of the party system to politics and the relation of the Church to party, class divisions, and the Marxian class-war, municipal government, the Press in its relation to the formation of public opinion, and some of the more important social issues, such as housing and unemployment which are in the forefront of political action in England.

The fundamental resolution, as finally passed after a long discussion is as follows:

The purpose of the State is to bind all men together in a justly ordered social life, and its authority ought to be generally accepted by Christians.

The duties of citizenship are a sacred obligation for Christian people. The authority of the State is limited by its function, and ought only to be challenged by the Christian conscience in the name of God. Christians should be willing, while their strength lasts, to spend and be spent in its service.

I wish to do no more here than to throw out this suggestion of an Indian Conference, in the hope that it may be taken up and discussed and the possibilities explored. There may be other ways of reaching the end. But I am convinced that no serious Christian man or woman who reads through the reports of this English Conference and thinks steadily over the analogous problems in India will fail to realize, that one of the burdens that now lie on the Christian people, India, and foreign, in this land, is to address themselves to the great task of translating the message of the Master into terms of the social, domestic and national life of India.

*NCCI Dalit And Tribal/Adivasi concern
campaign against Caste in Church*

**“No One can serve Christ and Caste”
Practise of Caste is Sin, and Untouchability Crime**

Discrimination based on Caste in your Church?

write to : dataconcerns@ncci1914.com

NCCI NEWS

NCCI-IDEA ISL 2.0 CONCLUDES, USHERING IN HOPE FOR CHURCHES AND THE HEARING-IMPAIRED COMMUNITY

The National Council of Churches in India–Indian Disability Ecumenical Accompaniment (NCCI-IDEA) hosted a memorable valedictory event for its Indian Sign Language (ISL) 2.0 Batch on June 9th, 2024. This course, which commenced on March 23rd, 2024, saw the enthusiastic participation of 30 students from various regions of India, including the North, Northeast, Central, and Southern states. The course was led by Ms Y Madhurya, whose extensive experience and dedication as an interpreter and teacher of Indian Sign Language greatly benefited the participants. Under her guidance, the students showed great progress, culminating in a celebratory event that highlighted their achievements.

The online valedictory ceremony, held at 6 PM, was a significant occasion attended by students, trainers, and special guests. Out of the 30 enrolled students, 25 received merit certificates, recognising their hard work and commitment to learning ISL. Pastor Rushi from the Nagpur Deaf Fellowship graced the event as the Chief Guest. In his address, he expressed profound joy and appreciation for the efforts of the students in breaking down communication barriers by learning ISL. Rev. Asir Ebenezer, in his valedictory address, inspired the students to continue their journey with ISL, encouraging them to engage with the hearing-impaired community around them. His words were a call to action, urging this ISL batch to make inclusivity a personal mission. Additionally, on Monday, June 10th, five students residing in Nagpur were given certificates offline at the NCCI Nagpur office by the General Secretary.

Students shared touching testimonies, expressing how the three-month course not only taught them a new language but also boosted their confidence and heightened their awareness of inclusivity. They spoke about the transformative experience of learning ISL and the sense of accomplishment they felt. With the conclusion of ISL 2.0, NCCI-IDEA is now looking forward to the next chapter. The success of this course opens the way for ISL 3.0, inviting more individuals to embark

on this rewarding journey. It could be your turn next to step into the world of the hearing-impaired community by learning their language and envisioning a more inclusive society. For more information on upcoming courses and how to enrol, follow NCCI's website, and social media or write to us at idea@ncci1914.com. Join us in making a difference by bridging communication gaps and promoting inclusivity through the learning of Indian Sign Language.

Rev Ribin John

Executive Secretary

Ecumenical Fora/ NCCI-NEFGS

**NO EXCUSE FOR ELDER ABUSE: NCCI ON
WORLD ELDER
ABUSE AWARENESS DAY**

The National Council of Churches in India (NCCI) – Commission on Youth Concerns organized a webinar on World Elder Abuse Awareness Day on June 15th, 2024 to discuss the various issues, violences, physical and mental abuse and challenges faced by elders and how they can prevent the elder abuse by taking help of other people and in some cases help from NGOs. This webinar gave insight of different types of elder abuses and some real stories shared by participants.

Rev. Rajesh Matthew, from Mar Thoma Prayojana Institute, Kearla, an old age home, shared his experience working with elders. He spoke about the issue of children abandoning their elderly parents and the importance of recognizing the value of elders as the backbone of society. Rev. Deepak Abraham from CNI also shared his experiences on elder abuse also shared insights on theological inclusivity encountered during his ministry.

Mr. Thayil Daniel Samuel Geontologist, Palliative Care counselor/volunteer., gave the keynote address on the realities of elder abuse in India. He discussed the country's changing demographics with a growing elderly population and increasing life expectancy. Dr. Sam explored the perspectives of both younger and older generations, underlining the need for improved communication and understanding. A short film reinforcing the message of "No excuse for Elder Abuse" was presented

during his session. Dr. Sam defined elder abuse, its prevalence, and risk factors as outlined in the WHO report of 2015, including factors like migration, disabilities, mental health, and social isolation. He explained the different types of elder abuse, which include physical, emotional, financial, neglect, abandonment, and sexual abuse. He elaborated on signs of abuse, highlighting verbal abuse as the most common form, and emphasized the impact of abuse on the physical and mental health of victims, including the loss of fundamental rights.

Empowering elders to protect themselves from abuse was a key part of Mr. Sam's presentation. He encouraged awareness of rights, seeking help when needed, avoiding pressured financial decisions, and maintaining mental and physical well-being. The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act 2007, a government initiative supporting elders, was explained by Dr. Sam. He also shared helpline numbers and resource websites.

This webinar led by Rev. Asher Noah, NCCI- Commission on Youth Concerns and Ms. Mihika Bhore Vice President- NCCI discussed about elder abuse from a psychological perspective.

The webinar provided valuable information and raised awareness about the critical issue of elder abuse in India. It offered resources and empowered participants to identify, prevent, and address this form of mistreatment.

Rev Asher Noah,
Executive Secretary
NCCI Commission on Youth Concerns.

ECUMENICAL ENTREPRENEURS FORUM EXPANDS:

New Members and Innovative Strategies Highlighted at the EEF Delhi Chapter's II Meeting

The second meeting of the Delhi Chapter of the NCCI-Ecumenical Entrepreneurs Forum was held on June 19, 2024, at the NCCI Office in Delhi. This meeting welcomed three new members to the chapter, demonstrating its increasing influence and dedication to building a collaborative network of Christian businesspeople in the city. The meeting was attended by NCCI officials, including Rev. Dr. Asir Ebenezer, General Secretary of NCCI, and Executive Secretaries Rev.

Dr. Abraham Mathew and Rev. Ribin John. The General Secretary emphasised the relevance of a unified national network of Christian entrepreneurs, highlighting the need for mutual support and innovative business practices aligned with Christian values.

The main session, led by Chapter Coordinator Mr. Samson Theodore, focused on the theme “Business Enablers: Cultivating a Culture of Innovative Strategies for Entrepreneurial Leadership.” In his talk, Mr. Theodore underscored entrepreneurship as a divine calling that transcends age and advocated for a culture of innovation and strategic leadership. He stressed the importance of entrepreneurs supporting each other in their journeys. Following the talk, the chapter engaged in a robust discussion on key issues such as using business as a mission avenue, tackling the challenges of corruption, and the importance of rejecting Islamophobia. The chapter also committed to developing an annual plan, meeting bimonthly at different member locations, and promoting inclusive business practices by creating job opportunities for persons with disabilities.

The meeting concluded on a high note, with members feeling inspired and equipped with practical strategies for ethical and innovative entrepreneurship.

Rev Ribin John

Executive Secretary

Ecumenical Fora/ NCCI-NEFGS

NCCI-IDEA campaigns for

Rights of persons with Disability, and Accessibility and Inclusion in Physical and Mind space

Need HELP?
Call **7028 400 222**
or Write to **idea@ncci1914.com**

WCC NEWS

WCC-LED CONSULTATION UNITES GLOBAL VOICES ON LAND, WATER, AND FOOD SECURITY

The World Council of Churches (WCC) cohosted a hybrid consultation in Geneva, focusing on the critical nexus of land, water, and food. The event convened distinguished international experts, community leaders, and activists to discuss sustainable solutions and the interdependencies of these vital resources.

The consultation featured both online and on-site speakers, including Prof. Pedro Arrojo, UN special rapporteur on the Right to Water; Dr Joann Lee, programme officer of the G20 Global Land Initiative for the UN Convention to Combat Desertification; and Sofia Espinosa, UN Food and Agriculture Organization, Land and Water tenure specialist. Onsite speakers included Rev. Dr Kenneth Mtata, WCC programme director for Public Witness and Diakonia; Dr Ramesh Sharma, general secretary of Ekta Parishad, a mass-based peoples' movement for land rights; and Dr Ana Maria Suarez Franco from Food First Information and Action Network International.

“We are here to understand how land, water, and food are interconnected and to develop integrated strategies for sustainable resource management,” said Mtata in his keynote address. “This nexus is crucial for achieving sustainable living for people and the planet, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals.”

Mtata also emphasized the role of faith in addressing these issues: “For us as the World Council of Churches, we take the faith-based dimension of this work seriously. While it is important to address land, water, and food issues holistically, it is even more important to use a rights-based approach. Climate change affects all three areas and exacerbates the problems, making our approach even more vital.”

The event highlighted the significant challenges related to land degradation, water scarcity, and food insecurity exacerbated by climate change. Sharma emphasized the importance of a community-centric approach to addressing these issues: “This is not only a focus

on providing access to these resources but also ensuring that the management and use of these resources is equitable and sustainable.”

Arrojo shared insights on the critical role of aquatic ecosystems and soil fertility in sustaining life and food production. “Preserving the good condition and sustainability of rivers, lakes, wetlands, and aquifers is essential to guarantee the human right to water and food,” he noted.

Participants also discussed the necessity of integrating traditional and Indigenous knowledge into modern practices. Espinosa stressed, “We must support communities in sharing their knowledge and experiences, as this is key to developing equitable and sustainable solutions.”

The consultation concluded with a call to action for collaborative efforts among faith communities, civil society organizations, and international bodies to implement holistic and rights-based approaches to resource management. Lee stressed, “We can collaborate to highlight the importance of faith institutions and actors in land and ecosystem restoration.”

Dinesh Suna, coordinator of the WCC Ecumenical Water Network and staff responsible for WCC Working Group on Land, Water, and Food Justice, moderated the session. “The WCC reaffirms its commitment to addressing the intertwined issues of land, water, and food through continued dialogue, policy advocacy, and community engagement,” he said.

WCC EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE CALLS FOR AN END TO THE INVASION AND OCCUPATION OF UKRAINIAN TERRITORY

The World Council of Churches (WCC) executive committee, in a minute on the escalation of the war in Ukraine, called for “an end to the invasion and occupation of Ukrainian territory, and the re-establishment of peace in the region.”

The minute reads: “We appeal also to the governments of Russia and Ukraine to respect the fundamental human and moral right of conscientious objection to military service, even in times of war.”

“We are appalled by the terrible toll in lives lost, livelihoods and communities destroyed, environmental harm, and wider conflict risks

resulting from this war, and call for the protection of civilians and civilian infrastructure, an end to the invasion and occupation of Ukrainian territory, and the re-establishment of peace in the region,” reads the text. “We appeal also to the governments of Russia and Ukraine to respect the fundamental human and moral right of conscientious objection to military service, even in times of war.”

The WCC executive committee commended the WCC general secretary’s efforts to address this crisis through dialogue, and urged the general secretary to redouble his efforts and to take all necessary measures to convene dialogue within the ecumenical fellowship.

The WCC executive committee is meeting in Bogotá, Colombia from 6-11 June, where the governing body is focusing on the business of the WCC and on absorbing the life and witness of churches at the heart of the Pilgrimage of Justice, Reconciliation, and Unity.

CCA NEWS

TRAINING PROSPECTIVE CHURCH LEADERS IN GOOD GOVERNANCE AND STEWARDSHIP IN PASTORAL MINISTRY A Joint Programme of CCA and Senate of Serampore

The Christian Conference of Asia (CCA), jointly with the Board of Theological Education of the Senate of Serampore Colleges (BTESSC) organized a national workshop on ‘Good Governance and Stewardship in Parish Ministry’.

The workshop was held at the Senate Centre for Extension and Pastoral Theology Research in Kolkata, India from 3 to 5 June 2024.

About 30 final year students pursuing their studies in Bachelor of Divinity Course from various theological institutions affiliated to the Senate of Serampore attended the workshop.

The aim of the workshop was to equip the ministerial candidates with the knowledge and skills necessary for effective governance and stewardship in their future parish ministries.

Rev. Prof. Eleazar S. Fernandez, a distinguished Professor Emeritus of Constructive Theology at the United Theological Seminary in the Philippines shared insights from his extensive academic pursuit. Rev. Asigor P. Sitanggang, Th.D, Th.D, of the Jakarta Theological Seminary expounded on how to apply biblical principles to teach what it means to be a good steward in the eyes of God and how to embody these qualities in pastoral ministry.

Key sessions facilitated included ‘Biblical foundations on Good Governance and Stewardship’, ‘Good Theology = Good Governance: Being God’s Stewards’, ‘Church Leadership Models and their Roots in Ecclesiology’, ‘Church as Christian Organisation’, ‘Financial Stewardship, Transparency and Overcoming Corruption’, ‘Integrity and Accountability in Parish Leadership’, ‘Human Resource Management, Conflict Resolution and Peacemaking’, ‘Fostering Good Governance and Pastoral Leadership in Digital Spheres’, and ‘Contextual Values: Indigenized Management Principles’.

Sharing feedback on the programme, Rev. Dr Rodinmawia Ralte, Professor and Dean of the Senate Centre for Extension and Pastoral Theological Research (SECP TRE) commented, “these intensive workshops on Good Governance and Stewardship are essential means to instill both Christian values in church administration as well as right management skills for students who will join Pastoral ministry after their Theological studies.”

The workshop was a resounding success, providing participants with valuable insights and practical tools to enhance their leadership and stewardship roles in their respective parishes.

GLOBAL CHRISTIAN FORUM

Message of the Fourth Global Gathering “That the World May Know”

The rain came with a cool breeze, driving away the humid heat through the open windows of the church. An auspicious blessing from God! So began the collective story of the 4th Global Gathering of the Global Christian Forum in Ghana, a country where Christianity is vibrant and thriving. An outpouring of hospitality and generosity characterised our time together from 16-19 April 2024.

The very first youth gathering in GCF's history preceded the main Forum from 13-15 April. The diversity and vision of the young adults gave energy to their own conversations about justice, hope, and reconciliation.

This is the 25th Anniversary of the Global Christian Forum, something we celebrated joyfully. Throughout its existence, the GCF has been a unique space for all major streams of Christianity to be together for encounter and prayer. It is the broadest expression of Christian faith and one that reflects the movement of the majority of churches from the global north to the global south.

“That the world may know that you have sent me and have loved them as you have loved me.” John 17:23

One in God

We want the world to know and to do so we must live the gospel in unity.

The charism of the Global Christian Forum is the sharing of faith stories. These personal stories act as bridges that help us foster mutual respect and embrace diversity by recognising Christ in the other. They help us move beyond a posture of “us” and “them.”

To share our personal stories is to witness to the resurrection of Christ together.

Broken in Humanity

Nevertheless, the world will not know Christ merely by our words, but by our actions.

During our time together in Ghana, we walked in the footsteps, on the sweat and blood, of millions of enslaved, dehumanised African men, women, and children at the Cape Coast Castle. We stood in the dark, stifling dungeons, spaces made more horrifying by the presence of a church directly above. Those above invoked blessings for the ships that would forcibly take the captives to the Americas, Caribbean, and Europe as objects of lucrative trade.

Sadly, as we continued to share amongst ourselves, we heard stories of continuing dehumanisation across the world today. Where human beings are oppressed and marginalised, there is a failure to recognise the

image and likeness of God in one another. When we destroy creation, we dishonour the Creator.

Gathering in the Wesley Cathedral, we were reminded through our worship of Christ's call for lamentation, for healing, and for reconciliation. Through the Lord, and with heart-felt repentance, we can rise out of the ashes of our brokenness with integrity, justice, and solidarity.

Healed Through Christ

We are empowered by the Spirit to act for the restoration of the world. The church must raise its prophetic voice.

The gifts of joy and hope also flourish in our contexts and churches. We shared these with one another and we raised our hearts and voices in prayer and fellowship as a witness to God's reconciling grace.

As the broken – and yet reconciling – Body of Christ, we can clearly hear the voice of the Shepherd who heals all wounds. Through the testimonies of pain and ever-enduring hope, God is speaking, calling us to deeper conversion and unity.

We know the very credibility of our faith depends on how we reflect the depth of God's love for all.

Sent Out

With this message, we – the participants of the 4th Global Gathering, call upon the churches throughout the world to continue to live out the charism of the Global Christian Forum.

In our diversity, may we be one in our Triune God.

In lamentation, may our hearts be broken by that which breaks God's heart.

In Christ, may we experience healing and reconciliation.

And in the Holy Spirit, may we be sent out with boldness and humility, to make God's transforming Spirit of forgiveness, justice, healing, restoration, grace, and salvation known.

BIBLE STUDY

JOSEPH'S NARRATIVE AS A PARADIGM TOWARDS TRUE STEWARDSHIP

*- Imtikumla Aier**

Joseph's narrative maintains its popularity by illustrating the revelation of God's presence and His plans to those who fix their gaze on or choose to rely on Him. This narrative is an amalgamation of blessing, sadness, jealousy, forgiveness, among other themes. However, the emphasis is drawn upon the theme of stewardship. In some selected passages from Chapter 39, the role of a steward is well defined. It reads, "steward" as "an overseer," literally meaning to manage or to serve. In simple terms, a steward is to manage something on someone's behalf, a caretaker of whatever is entrusted to one's care. Regardless of whether it is acknowledged or not, God recalls humankind to steward the responsibilities delegated to them. Hence, this chapter draws readers toward understanding the true essence of stewardship.

The context of this chapter is set against a tense tone. Joseph, as young as 17, as said by scholars, had to go through a series of migrations. It begins with his brothers trading him to the Midianite and Ishmaelite traders, and then to Potiphar in the land of Egypt. Joseph, from what he went through, portrays that he was not just a slave but rather a "sold slave." In the midst of these unpleasant circumstances, he found favour in the eyes of his master because the Lord was with him. Joseph, however, was not without temptation. The passages describe him as stunningly handsome, well-built, and fair, which caused Potiphar's wife to develop a sense of lust toward him, eventually leading to his imprisonment despite his innocence. This particular incident may seem daunting or disappointing for some, while for others it raises questions about how a person who is obedient and faithful to his master can suffer untold misery when proven innocent. Furthermore, it raises questions about the presence of God and the favour of his master during times of despair.

The powerlessness of Joseph as steward to a human master, a slave, and a foreigner is portrayed, enabling readers to understand that humanly

* Imtikumla Aier is a postgraduate in the Old Testament and currently serving as a teaching faculty at Eastern Bible College, Dimapur, Nagaland.

demonstrated power is an unstable source. A steward is not determined or directed by human masters; rather, this narrative shows the divine portrayal of true stewardship and its qualities. Just when Joseph thought his career was ending abruptly, a new role of stewardship awaited him as keeper of the prison. Joseph's role as a true steward begins and ends in the favour of God. From the initial stage of the narrative, God's favour upon Joseph is indicated: "and the Lord was with Joseph," and ends with the verse that says, "the Lord made it prosper." These points reflect how God prepared Joseph as a true steward.

1. Joseph Knew the Lord was with Him

The effects of divine blessing flow outwardly, just as in Genesis 12:2-3, which may have led to the expectation: 'Yahweh blessed the Egyptian's house for Joseph's sake' (Gen. 39:5). Joseph was the conduit of a reciprocal blessing, and his social position rose within Potiphar's household. As a young man, Joseph understood his role as a steward; he was aware of the favour of God upon him. Through this understanding, he discovered his call to serve both God and his earthly master. The chapter starts with the favour of God upon Joseph; however, Joseph reciprocated in every possible way. He did not comply with worldly wisdom and knowledge but fixed his eyes on God alone, which led to him being lifted to greater heights on earth. Despite going through much as a young slave, Joseph discovered his gift from God, which was to "serve." He did not boast or become arrogant but rather, through his gift, chose to serve God and his earthly master faithfully. Verses 2-6 describe Joseph's rise in Potiphar's esteem: firstly, he was promoted to work indoors instead of being sent into the fields; secondly, he became Potiphar's personal attendant; ultimately, he was put in charge of his household and entrusted with all his possessions. When he showed his master that he was a faithful steward, Potiphar trusted all in his care, as v. 5 says, "all that he had" was entrusted to Joseph. This success was not just about Joseph's achievements but about the reason for that success: the Lord was with Joseph. Verse 6 reinforces Joseph's role as a steward, stating that Potiphar left everything in Joseph's hands, meaning he entrusted all that he had to Joseph and abandoned his interest in what Joseph was doing because he was convinced that his servant was doing the best for him. What makes Joseph distinct is that he understood the favour of God upon him, which enabled him to serve faithfully.

The narrative clearly points out that the Lord was with Joseph, but understanding the presence of God in his life was his role. How was

he able to understand this presence? He understood his gift and showed clarity, revealing that he knew the Lord was with him. The interpretation or understanding of stewardship in this generation often carries little weight; it is taken lightly and is understood without considering the responsibilities that come with it, such as righteousness, justice, fairness, and equality. Often, the concept of headship, control, and power is attached to its meaning. Knowing the presence of God and His subtle influence over humanity is crucial for understanding stewardship, which enables one to discover ways to serve God and the community.

2. Joseph was Trustworthy and Faithful

Joseph found favour in the eyes of God and his master yet was not without trials and temptations. Verse 7 explores this new challenge for Joseph as his master's wife "cast her eyes on Joseph," indicating a lustful desire toward him. Joseph's moral encounter with Potiphar's wife was also a trial for the youth because his faithfulness to God was at stake: "How then could I do such a wicked thing and sin against God?" (v. 9). He does not merely rebuke such action but questions it, implying that there was a standard of righteousness demanded from him. For Joseph, refusing this advance was not enough; his questions showed his commitment to his calling to be a faithful steward. When Joseph refers to "My Master," it indicates his sense of duty to the man who had entrusted everything to him. This demonstrates his faithfulness to his master and to God. According to Moses's law (Lev. 20:10; Deut. 22:22), an adulterer would be put to death, and Joseph followed this law righteously. He understood that this adulterous "sin" was not only against God but also against his earthly master, Potiphar. He stood firm in his principles even when wrongfully accused and imprisoned; he again found favour in the eyes of the prison chief, and "all" the prisoners and "all" activities fell under his supervision (vv. 22; cf. vv. 5-6). As Corinthians 4:2 says, "it is required of stewards that they be found faithful," and Joseph took this role seriously.

3. Joseph was Always Prepared

Joseph was a man of sincerity, integrity, and vigilance. Verse 12 holds this testament when he was lured by his master's wife: "I cannot sin against my master; I cannot sin against your marriage; I cannot sin against you; I cannot sin against God, and this is a sin of great wickedness." Joseph sees it for what it is and prepares for what is to come. He counters the sin presented before him. He flees from temptation because he was

prepared. He does not conceal what is sinful; he declares where his allegiance, intentions, and affections lie. The definition of sin is distorted today; it is defined by one's situation and circumstances, not by how it is defined in the Bible. For many reasons, Joseph was prepared to stand against this. Even his unfair dismissal and imprisonment, typical suffering of the righteous, did not stop him from proclaiming what was sinful in his eyes. As Prov. 24:16 says, "For a righteous man falls seven times and rises again." His calling to be a steward was extraordinary, and these factors strengthened him to be courageous and prepared for all circumstances ahead. This allows readers to understand that being a steward demands preparedness—not indulging in sinful ways but also confidently proclaiming what sin is and standing firm in its principles.

Conclusion

Humankind are the sole managers and ambassadors of God, the creator and sustainer. Joseph had a divine and earthly master to whom he was faithful. Looking at the context, Joseph, being at his prime age, could have enjoyed his position with luxuries, but he chose to be faithful. He understood that his role as a steward was sacred. Even at the lowest point in his life, in a foreign land with no prospect of release, God initiated the steps that brought about Joseph's deliverance, which he did not foresee. God's timing is never too early nor too late; it is always on time. Joseph's life transition is full of ups and downs, but God used him in His right time. He was adored by his father but sold off by his brothers out of jealousy. He then found favour in the eyes of his foreign master but was tempted by his wife and sent to prison. Just when he was serving well by entering a new era of deliverance, all his hopes seemed to crumble. But his role did not end there; God's calling for him to be a steward was fixed, and he was uplifted to greater heights. At present, many ignore this call due to the fast-paced generation and the influence of growing cultural and addictive trends. In such situations, the role of true stewardship is distorted by attaching insignificant human-made qualities. The narrative shows the importance of recommitting to and revisiting one's role as a true steward. It allows all individuals to see the essence of true stewardship in the ordinary; it is not the extraordinary that takes the trophy but the humble, the committed, and the one who is ready to let God do the ordinary. Let this be a reminder that the role of a true steward is found not in material trappings of life but in the means and ways through which God reveals Himself to humankind.

Vedhik IAS Academy

in collaboration with

National Council of Churches in India CIVIL SERVICES COACHING PROGRAM

PROGRAMMES PRIMED FOR CIVIL SERVICES COACHING

When you are with Vedhik, it doesn't matter which part of the world you are in. At present, we have 129 centers in India and a presence in more than 14 countries. Our online programmes are structured to build strong foundations for you, improve your knowledge base and develop analytical skills.

Let your journey to success in the Indian & civil services examinations begin here. Choose the programme that suits you.

SPRINT :

Duration : 1 years Programme

Eligibility: Graduates and Working Professional

RUN A MILE :

Duration : 2 years Programme

Eligibility: UG & PG Students ,Graduates and Working Professional

MARATHON :

Duration : Four year Programme

Eligibility: Plus One and Plus Two Students

CROSS COUNTRY :

Duration : Six years Programme

Eligibility: 8th, 9th , 10th standard students.

*We have fixed one time fee of Rs.29,999/- plus GST for the Civil Services Coaching Programme.

GATEWAY :

Duration : One year programme

Eligibility: Middle school students (6th to 8th)

*We have fixed one time fee of Rs.5,000/- plus GST

REGISTER NOW

Contact us for Registraion

✉ ncci@vedhikiasacademy.org

☎ 011-2373 06 57 | +91 9778 410 461

🏠 National Council of Churches in India (NCCI)
#403, CNI Bhavan.

16, Pandit Pant Marg.

New Delhi – 110 001. India.

🌐 ncci1914.com

Christian
Medical
Association of
India

www.CMAI.org

CMAI INVITES APPLICATIONS FOR THE POST OF GENERAL SECRETARY (CEO)

CMAI is a national NGO and a fellowship of Christian Hospitals and Christian Healthcare Professionals in India. CMAI works to serve the church in India to equip, assist and encourage it in its ministry of health, healing and wholeness.

CMAI invites application from eligible, interested and committed Christian candidates with good standing for the post of General Secretary (CEO) of CMAI. This is a leadership position, working with Health Professionals, Mission Hospitals, Churches, Civil Societies, Government, representing Christian health work and provides exciting opportunities to lead transformational changes in health, training and policy making. The details and requirement regarding the position are as given below:

Age limit: between preferable 40 years to 55 years.

Full time Position requires to be based in Delhi.

Qualifications: Post Graduate degree in any healthcare discipline.

Experience:

- Having preferably minimum 15 years of experience out of which 5 years in a senior leadership/administrative position
- A good understanding of healthcare service delivery and of the hospital sector
- Working with hospitals or development agencies related to health
- Nurturing Christians of different healthcare professions
- Networking with Government, national/international agencies
- Willingness to travel

Desirable Qualities:

- Member of a Church Affiliated to National Council of Churches in India

Other Attributes:

- Spiritually well-grounded and held in high esteem by society
- An ecumenical outlook and a firm belief in the ethos of CMAI
- Able to relate to the government, leaders of churches and of the CMAI network
- Preferably CMAI member for a minimum of 3 years

Remuneration: Salary & perks will be as per CMAI norms.

Last date to apply: 15. 10. 2024

Send in your detailed CV to: The Dy Administrative Manager, CMAI, Plot No: 2, A3 Local Shopping Centre, Janakpuri, New Delhi – 110058 | hr@cmai.org

THE UNITED THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE, BANGALORE

Prepares candidates for Pastoral Ministry, Teaching Ministry and Church-related Services

COURSES OFFERED FOR THE ACADEMIC YEAR 2025-2026

No.	Courses Offered	Deg./Dip.	Duration
1.	Doctor of Theology Degree of the Senate of Serampore	D.Th.	3 years
2.	Master of Theology Degree of the Senate of Serampore	M.Th.	2 years
3.	Bachelor of Divinity Degree of the Senate of Serampore	B.D.	4 years
4.	Bachelor of Christian Studies, Distance Education of the Senate of Serampore	B.C.S.	4 years
5.	Diploma in Christian Studies, Distance Education of the Senate of Serampore	Dip.C.S.	2 years
6.	Diploma for Proficiency in Counselling, College Degree	D.P.C.	1 year
7.	Certificate in Christian Service, College Degree	C.C.S.	1 year
8.	Diploma in Women's Studies, College Degree	D.W.S.	6 months
9.	Master of Science in Counselling Psychology, (in Association with Martin Luther Christian University, an UGC Recognized Private University)	M.Sc. (Couns. Psy.)	2 years
10.	Post Graduate Diploma for Proficiency in Counselling (in Association with Martin Luther Christian University, an UGC Recognized Private University)	PGDPC	1 year

Doctor of Theology		Degree of the Senate of Serampore College		Master of Theology	
D.Th.	3 Years	Old Testament		M.Th.	2 Years
D.Th.	3 Years	New Testament		M.Th.	2 Years
D.Th.	3 Years	Christian Theology		M.Th.	2 Years
D.Th.	3 Years	Christian Ethics			
D.Th.	3 Years	History of Christianity		M.Th.	2 Years
D.Th.	3 Years	Missiology		M.Th.	2 Years
D.Th.	3 Years	Christian Ministry - Pastoral Counselling		M.Th.	2 Years
*D.Th.	3 Years	Religions – Hinduism		M.Th.	2 Years
		Religions - Primal		M.Th.	2 Years
		Women's Studies		M.Th.	2 Years

* Subject to the approval of Senate of Serampore.

	B.D.	M.Th.	D.Th.	BCS	DCS	M.Sc. (Couns. Psy.)	DPC/ PGDPC	DWS	CCS
Application Registration Fee	500/-	650/-	800/-	600/-	600/-	500/-	250/-	250/-	250/-
Last date of submission	15 th November 2024					
Late fee + Form fee	900/-	1100/-	1300/-	800/-	800/-	700/-	500/-	500/-	500/-
Last date with late fee	22 nd November 2024					
Entrance & Interview	15-16 Jan. 25	22-23 Jan. 25	30 Jan. 25	-	-	-	-	-	-

Please note that no application will be entertained after the last date as mentioned above.

Scholarships: Limited scholarships are available for needy candidates after the successful completion of their first year B.D./M.Th. studies.

Kindly remit all payments through any one of the following payment methods:

- Online fund transfer via NEFT/ RTGS / Internet Banking / Mobile banking / IMPS to **UNITED THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE, SAVING BANK ACCOUNT, A/C NO. 0429101003275** with **Canara Bank, Benson Town Branch, IFSC Code: CNRB0000429.**
- UPI payment portal to **492082003275@cnrb**
- Money Order/ Demand Draft/ Cheque drawn in favour of **"United Theological College, Bangalore"**

Kindly address all enquiries to:

THE REGISTRAR, THE UNITED THEOLOGICAL COLLEGE, 63, MILLER'S ROAD, BENSON TOWN, J.C. NAGAR POST, BANGALORE - 560 006, INDIA.

Mob. 9611270124, Email: registrarutc@gmail.com, Website: www.utc.edu.in

ADVERTISEMENT RATES IN THE NCC REVIEW

	<i>Full Page</i>	<i>Half Page</i>	<i>Inside Cover</i>	<i>Cover</i>
Single	Rs. 1200	Rs. 800	Rs. 1400	Rs.1600
Multiple*	Rs. 900	Rs. 650	Rs. 1050	Rs. 1200
*Multiple rates applicable per insertion for at least three consecutive insertions. All other terms and conditions shall remain same.				

NCC REVIEW REVISED SUBSCRIPTION RATES FROM 4/2016

	1 year	3 year	5 year
Indian Subscriptions (<i>Regular</i>)	INR 250	INR 500	INR 800
Indian Subscriptions (<i>Discounted for Theological Educators, Pastors, Evangelists, Students - Individuals only. NOT for Organisations, Institutions, Librarians, etc.</i>)	INR 200	INR350	INR 550
Bulk order (over 50 copies for Indian Subscriptions)	10% off		
UK Subscriptions	GBP 31	-	-
USA, South America, Canada, Europe, Africa, Asia, Australia, New Zealand, Subscriptions	USD 45	-	-

PAYMENT MODES:

VPP: Place your subscription order by email: ncci@ncci1914.com or nccreview@ncci1914.com (Rs.20/- added to subscription cost)

Demand Draft: To be drawn in favour of "National Council of Churches in India" payable at Nagpur.

Cheque: To be drawn in favour of "National Council of Churches in India" (Please add Rs. 20/- for outstation cheques).

Money order: To be sent to: The Editor, NCC Review, Nagpur.

Bank Transfer: Bank name: INDIAN BANK
 Branch: NAGPUR
 IFSC CODE: IDIB000N007
 A/C NAME: NATIONAL COUNCIL OF CHURCHES REVIEW
 A/C NUMBER: 496991073

ISSN 0975 - 1882

RNP/NPCity/237/2018-2020

PRGI Reg. No. 72101/99. Registered with the Registrar of Newspapers for India

Price: ₹ 23/-

Date of posting 20th of every month

NCCI COMMUNICATIONS

*Get NCCI news updates and stay connected
on our network through your comments*

Website: www.ncci1914.com

Facebook: facebook.com/nccionline

Twitter: twitter.com/nccionline

YouTube: youtube.com/nccinet

SMS: Register your mobile number to get NCCI alerts/updates on your phone. Details on our website

News Update: Register your email address to receive NCCI news updates by email. Registration details on our website

NCCI NEWS app for Android devices
NCCI NEWS app for Android™ devices
on Google Play™

Download the app on your mobile device.

Search for "ncci" on Google Play on your device.

NCC Review : To subscribe to India's oldest (*since 1862*) Ecumenical journal **NCC Review** download the subscription form on the link: <https://ncci1914.com/ncc-review/>